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Position Reconstruction Based on Prompt Scintillation

Light in XENONnT Exploiting Deep Learning

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To whom else but you?

Abstract

The XENONnT experiment consists of a dual-phase time projection chamber (TPC) filled with liquid and gaseous xenon. It is designed to detect very rare interactions of dark matter candidates inside the liquid xenon. The deposition of energy inside the sensitive volume generates a prompt signal of scintillation photons, S1, and ionization electrons. The electrons are guided by an electric field to the gaseous phase at the top of the TPC and create there a delayed and proportional scintillation light, S2. The conventional way to reconstruct the (x,y) position inside the sensitive volume exploits the S2 signal detected by the light sensors in the top array. The z position is obtained from the time difference between the S1 and S2 signal. This thesis proposes a novel method for three-dimensional position reconstruction based exclusively on the S1 signal. It employs a convolutional neural network that takes the measurements of the light sensors at the top and bottom array as input. A simulation and a data-driven model are developed. The latter one obtains a spatial resolution of $r_{68\%} \simeq 2$ cm for S1 signal sizes above 10^5 photoelectrons. This new technique can be applied to improve event quality selections, to map possible charge insensitive regions of the detector, and to analyze events without a reliable S2 signal.

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Preface

An experiment is a question
which science poses to Nature and
a measurement is the recording of
Nature's answer.

Max Planck

Since its origins, humans have tried to understand the world around them with amazement and wonder. Particle physics is one of the purest intellectual developments of this inborn desire. The aim of this field is to know and to describe the smallest building blocks of Nature and to develop a theory on how they interact with each other.

It is downright fair to say that in 2021 this search is not finished yet. Particularly in the last century, important progress was made with the formulation and the experimental validation of the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics, culminating in the discovery of the Higgs boson announced on 4 July 2012 by the ATLAS and CMS experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN [1, 2].

Today we know from the cosmological parameters [3] that the energy budget of the Universe has the following contributions: $(30.89 \pm 0.62)\%$ from matter, $(68.89 \pm 0.56)\%$ from dark energy, and $(0.07 \pm 0.19)\%$ from spatial curvature, which is consistent with a flat Universe. From the baryon¹ density parameter and dark matter's (DM) one, we know that SM particles contribute only for $\simeq 4.90\%$ to the total matter while $\simeq 26.07\%$ is due to DM.

At the present time the dark side of the Universe is still a mystery: concretely the composition of $\simeq 94.96\%$ of the Universe is unknown. Over the last decades, a strong evidence for the existence of DM has been collected and countless models to explain its nature have been formulated. The possibility of its detection in the next years is relevant, even if not assured. This is one of the main reasons why DM is an interesting field to study now and one of the most quoted to open the doors to new physics, beyond the standard model (BSM).

¹Following the convention present in the literature we call baryons and leptons together baryons, since the former are more relevant for the energy budget.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction to Dark Matter

The following chapter presents a brief history of the DM puzzle, what has been learned about its features over the past four decades and what are the most quoted candidates for its solution.

History

In the literature, one of the first mentions of DM was made by Lord Kelvin in 1904, he inferred the number of dark bodies in the Milky Way from the observed velocity dispersion of the stars orbiting around the centre of the galaxy. From this argument, he predicted the mass of the galaxy, which seemed significantly different from the estimation of the total mass of visible stars. Lord Kelvin thus concluded: "many of our stars, perhaps a great majority of them, may be dark bodies." [4].

The work of Lord Kelvin was studied and commented two years after by Henri Poincaré, who used the term “dark matter” for the first time. He disagreed with Lord Kelvin’s estimate and wrote that “since his number is comparable to that which the telescope gives, then there is no dark matter, or at least not so much as there is of shining matter.” [5]. The name “dark matter” was introduced to point to a type of matter with gravitational interaction but without the electromagnetic one, resulting in an opaque component. However, the present observation does not exclude DM particles to have a tiny electric charge (see [section 1.2](#)).

In 1921 Albert Einstein was the first one to apply the viral theorem to a celestial system, precisely the globular cluster Messier 13, to look for traces of dark energy. However, he got a constraint on the abundance of DM in that system concluding that “the non-luminous mass contributes no higher order of magnitude to the total mass than does the luminous mass.” [6].

In 1933 the Swiss-American astronomer Fritz Zwicky in his work [7] studied the dynamics of more than 800 galaxies in the Coma cluster. Referring to the redshifts of the galaxies, measured by E. Hubble and M. Humanson in 1931, he pointed out that their dispersion velocity was too high to keep the system stable. Applying the viral theorem to infer the average mass density of the cluster from the velocity dispersion, he found that the obtained value was much higher than the one predicted from visible matter. In other words, it appeared to be more gravitating matter than the one which interacts with us through the electromagnetic force.

1.1 Indications of the Existence of Dark Matter

In the following sections we will briefly discuss what today are considered the main indications of the existence of DM. They come from a very wide range of astronomical scales, from a few kiloparsecs (the dimension of small galaxies) to the whole size of the observable Universe. It is somehow important to notice that all the evidences include gravitational effects of DM, while a phenomenon due to DM other than gravitational has yet to be discovered.

1.1.1 Galactic Scale: Rotation Curves

One of the most prominent and famous evidence for DM on galactic scales is the measurements of the circular velocity of stars and gas in the galactic disks as a function of their distance from the centre, i.e. the galactic rotation curves. The expected behaviour would be to see a decreasing velocity at large radii, following the Kepler's law $v_r \propto r^{-1/2}$, but the measured rotation curves are flat even at large distances from the galactic centre (see figure 1.1). In fact, at small enough radii for the mass of the galaxy $M(r)$, assuming a uniform density ρ , we have that $M(r) \propto \rho r^3$ and a linear behaviour for the velocity. At large enough radii, all the mass is concentrated within that radius, therefore $M(r) \simeq \text{const}$ and consequently one should observe the expected Keplerian decrease $v_r \propto r^{-1/2}$.

Since the mid-1960s Vera Rubin studied rotation curves of spiral galaxies starting with Andromeda Galaxy (M31) [8]. She used the sensitive spectrograph built by Kent Ford to detect signals coming from H-II regions of ionized atomic hydrogen at different distances from the galaxy centre. The anomalous behaviour was confirmed later also by radio-observations using the Doppler shift of the 21 cm hyperfine transition of neutral hydrogen.

The obtained results can be explained if we assume that all galaxies are embedded in a large halo of DM (see figure 1.2). The flat rotation curves are achieved for a spherical halo with mass distribution $\rho_{\text{halo}} \propto r^{-2}$.

Figure 1.1: The observed rotation curve of the M33 (or NGC 598), also known as Triangulum Galaxy. It is a spiral galaxy 2.73 million light-years from Earth. Plot taken from [9].

Figure 1.2: Illustration of the structure of a generic spiral galaxy embedded in a large spherical DM halo. Plot taken from [10].

1.1.2 Gravitational Lensing

Gravitational lensing is the effect predicted by General Relativity which consists in the deviation of the trajectory of photons when they pass close to a massive cosmic object.

This effect can be used to map DM halos distribution at distances beyond from baryonic disk, i.e. > 100 kpc from galactic centres, which constitutes a limit for the analysis of DM distribution using rotation curves. In this case, the bending of the signals coming from an extremely luminous object like the quasars, i.e. active galactic nucleus, can be used for the analysis. Comparing multiple image copies obtained by means of gravitational lensing effect, the distribution of DM can be mapped. An example of this kind of study is the one for MACS J0416.1-2403 galaxy cluster [11].

1.1.3 The Scale of Galaxy Clusters

The approach followed by Zwicky, i.e. the application of the virial theorem, is not the only one possible to estimate the total mass of an entire ensemble of galaxies, also known as cluster. This can also be done by means of gravitational lensing or studying the profile of the X-ray emission of the intracluster medium, which is a superheated plasma that permeates the galaxy cluster. Another way by which one can map intracluster medium is via the Sunyaev-Zel'dovich effect, that consists in the inverse Compton effect of CMB photons. Through all these methods one can estimate the gravitational mass of the cluster and comparing it with the "visible mass" can conclude that it is much larger.

Another very interesting phenomenon that can occur at the cluster level, even if it is quite rare, is provided by the observation of the so-called Bullet Cluster (1E 0657-56).

A cluster is mainly composed of galaxies, intracluster medium and DM fluid. Those elements behave in a different way during a collision, allowing them to be studied separately. In 1E0657-56, about 150 million years ago, two clusters collided in a direction close to the perpendicular to our line of sight. The first component, the galaxies, behave as point-like non-interacting particles and during the collision, they continued the motion along their own trajectory. Intracluster medium has a large self-interaction and was spread throughout the two incident clusters after the collision.

Figure 1.3: Adapted image of Bullet Cluster (1E0657-56). The red population (intracluster medium) is from X-ray observation and blue clump (dark matter) is revealed from the weak-lensing mass map. Yellow and white blobs are galaxies determined from optical measurement.

Lastly, DM fluid passed through the interaction region and its distribution now coincide with that of the galaxies of the two clusters. The distribution of DM fluid was inferred by means of gravitational lensing. At a statistical significance of 8σ it was found a spatial offset of the centre of the total mass from the centre of the baryonic mass peak, this fact proves that the majority of the matter in the system is unseen. This analysis is a powerful evidence of DM, which is independent of assumptions regarding the nature of the gravitational force law.

1.1.4 Cosmological Scales: Cosmic Microwave Background

In the present subsection the amount of DM is not considered in a limited portion of the Universe but in its entirety. This is possible by analyzing the most important source of data of the early Universe found so far: the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB).

After about 380,000 years from the birth of the Universe, when its temperature was around 3000 K (approximately 2700 °C) electrons and photons decouples and the latter started streaming unimpeded through the Universe. Photons from that very primordial era can be detected today, albeit much less energetic since the expansion of space causes a relevant increase in their wavelength. This radiation is known as CMB and its spectrum is precisely described by a black body emission whose temperature reads [12]:

$$T_{\text{CMB}} = (2.7255 \pm 0.006) \text{ K} . \quad (1.1)$$

Small relative fluctuations in its temperature can be detected at level of $\delta T/T_{\text{CMB}} \sim 10^{-5}$. As CMB temperature is a two-dimensional field, which can be described in angular coordinate, it can be expanded in spherical harmonics. Considering the temperature

Figure 1.4: Planck 2018 temperature power spectrum. The six parameter Λ CDM theoretical spectrum best fit is plotted in light blue in the upper panel. Residuals with respect to the model are shown in the middle panel. The bottom panel displays the difference between the 2015 and 2018 coadded high-multipole spectra (green points). The 1σ region corresponds to the binned data errors.

anisotropies they can be written as:

$$\frac{\delta T}{T_{\text{CMB}}}(\vartheta, \varphi) := \frac{T(\vartheta, \varphi) - T_{\text{CMB}}}{T_{\text{CMB}}} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-1}^1 a_{lm} Y_{lm}(\vartheta, \varphi). \quad (1.2)$$

For $l = 0$, the mean temperature of the CMB (T_{CMB}) is obtained, which is also known as CMB monopole. For $l = 1$, the CMB dipole is recovered and it represents the larger anisotropy, of the order of 10^{-3} . This effect is frame-dependent and it is interpreted as a Doppler shift due to the motion of our system with respect to the CMB rest frame. This means that the Earth is not a comoving observer: CMB photons coming from the direction we are currently heading towards get blue-shifted, the photons in the opposite direction get red-shifted. Therefore, this dipole moment does not encode any primordial information. Anisotropies in CMB temperature at higher order multipoles ($l \geq 2$) are mainly due to perturbations in the density of the early Universe, at the time in which photons decouples. Despite the smallness of these inhomogeneities, their existence has allowed the formation of structures such as galaxies.

Before recombination, the primordial bath was formed by different species of particles: neutrinos, DM, photons, protons, and electrons. The last three form a very tightly coupled photon-baryon fluid, as electrons interacts through Thomson scattering with photons and through Coulomb scattering with protons. Because of tiny matter density inhomogeneities present in the plasma, the gravity force pushes matter from under-dense

Figure 1.5: Planck 2018 temperature power spectrum for a DM density contribution Ω_c varying between 0.11 and 0.43. Figure taken from [13]

to over-dense regions. Following that stream and being strongly coupled in the fluid, photons counteract this effect with the increase of their radiation pressure. The result of these two opposite forces in the matter-radiation plasma is an oscillatory motion, known as acoustic oscillations, which determine the shape of the spectrum of the CMB (see figure 1.4). Here the role of DM is crucial in creating the gravitational potential wells affecting the oscillations of the photon-baryon fluid.

The detailed analysis of the peaks of the power spectrum allows to obtain important physical information about the Universe. From the position of the first peak can be inferred that the Universe is very close to be spatially flat. Generally speaking, the odd numbered acoustic peaks are related to the falling of plasma into gravitational potential wells and they are also known as compression peaks, while the even numbered to the rarefaction of plasma and they are also known as expansion peaks. If the relative baryon content in the plasma is higher, the compression peaks get higher, because baryons contribute to the gravitational potential, while expansion peaks get lower, because the pressure decreases. The amount of baryon can be checked in many independent ways in the power spectrum, e.g. baryons decrease the frequency of the oscillations, pushing the position of the peaks to slightly higher multipoles l , this behaviour can be disentangled from the effect of other parameters. An increase of the total matter density, which is dominated by DM, reduces the height of all peaks (see figure 1.5).

From a technical and detailed analysis of the power spectrum, based on the explained effects, we can obtain the total amount of matter Ω_m , the amount of baryonic matter Ω_b , i.e. coupled to the photon bath, and the amount of DM Ω_c [3]:

$$\Omega_m h^2 = 0.1428 \pm 0.0011, \quad (1.3)$$

$$\Omega_b h^2 = 0.02233 \pm 0.00015, \quad (1.4)$$

$$\boxed{\Omega_c h^2 = 0.120 \pm 0.001.} \quad (1.5)$$

From this result, we can conclude that DM must be non-baryonic and the most natural idea is to add new particle(s) not coupled to the photon bath at the time of recombination with a density approximately five times higher than the one for baryons.

Figure 1.6: Ultra deep field image taken by Hubble Space Telescope (left) and the fake observation produced with the simulation Illustris (right), images taken from [17]. Good agreement can be seen considering as a metric the degree of structure.

1.1.5 Structure Formation

The cosmology and astronomy communities have been making a big endeavour to understand the origin and the distribution of large scale structures (LSS), i.e. galaxies, clusters and super-clusters. Currently, most of the knowledge about them comes from the cosmic microwave background maps, spectroscopic surveys, gravitational lensing and Lyman- α line measurements of quasars. In the standard paradigm, LSS are thought arose from small primordial inhomogeneities generated during the inflationary era, which evolved under the opposite effects of gravity and the Hubble expansion. A widely used method to study this kind of phenomena is to perform N-body hydrodynamical simulations of galaxy formation in large cosmological volumes as carried out by IllustrisTNG project [14] [15]. The output of this kind of simulations can be compared to the spectroscopic galaxy survey, like 2dF Galaxy Redshift Survey [16] or to the observation of space telescopes (see figure 1.6). Studying changes in the results of simulations varying physical parameters can be a way by which infer physical features of the Universe. It is well known, for instance, that if DM is a particle and it is relativistic at the time of structure formations, the relative size of structures would be smeared out, for this reason DM cannot be “hot”.

1.2 Inferred Features of Particle Candidate

The solutions suggested for the “DM puzzle” can be classified at least in two sets: in the first, one or more DM particles are added to the SM, in the second one modified gravity paradigms are proposed. From here onwards, we will stay in the first set because the present work comes in the context of the direct experimental search for particle DM. Although it is not currently known the nature of DM, over the decades it has been possible to infer some properties that are reported shortly in what follows. Here we are only assuming that all the DM is made of a single particle candidate χ with mass m_χ .

- **Darkness.**

We know that DM takes its name from the fact that it does not interact electromagnetically. However, observation does not exclude DM particles to

have indeed a tiny electric charge whose limit depends on the model, for more information see [18].

- **Coldness.**

DM needs to be non-relativistic when the Universe had a temperature around $T \simeq 1 - 10$ keV, otherwise it smears out structure formation. This feature rules out thermal candidates with mass $m_\chi < 1 - 10$ keV such as SM neutrinos [19].

- **Mass.**

Observations do not place stringent constraints on the mass of DM. Assuming that it is a new elementary particle, here model-independent limits are discussed.

Firstly, we have a theoretical upper bound, in fact we do not expect any elementary particles heavier than the Planck mass. Otherwise, the Compton wavelength of the particle would be smaller than its Schwarzschild radius, forming a black hole. So we can conclude that:

$$m_\chi \lesssim 10^{19} \text{ GeV} .$$

To estimate a lower bound we can look at the smallest DM-dominated structures observed: the dwarf spheroidal (dSph) galaxies with $R_{\text{DW}} \sim 1 \text{ kpc} = 1.6 \times 10^{26} \text{ eV}^{-1}$. We can set two constraints, depending on whether the DM is a boson or a fermion, requiring that DM needs to be able to localize within the size of dwarf galaxies.

- **Boson:** computing the de Broglie wavelength of a DM particle and asking that $\lambda_{\text{DM}} < R_{\text{d}}$ we get:

$$m_{\text{DM}} \gtrsim 10^{-22} \text{ eV} .$$

- **Fermion:** the constraint is much stronger for fermions due to the Pauli exclusion principle, this is also known as Tremaine-Gunn bound. The idea is that there is a limit on the density of fermions in the phase space. If we call g_χ the number of internal degrees of freedom of the DM particle candidate and σ_{dSph} the velocity dispersion of stars in the dwarf galaxy, the following final result is achieved [20]:

$$m_\chi > 101 \text{ eV} \left(\frac{100 \text{ km s}^{-1}}{\sigma_{\text{dSph}}} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \left(\frac{1 \text{ kpc}}{r} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} g_\chi^{-1/4} . \quad (1.6)$$

This bound is another reason why active neutrinos cannot be a candidate for DM. The constraints for many sub-cases of DM candidates have been updated by more recent work with respect to (1.6). The order of magnitude reached by the latest analyzes can be summarized in $m_{\text{DM}} \gtrsim \text{keV}$ (see [21, 22] for more details.).

- **Self-interaction.**

An analysis of the Bullet Cluster described in section 1.1.3 allows to find a limit on the self interaction cross section of DM particles [23]:

$$\sigma/m_\chi \lesssim 1.25 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1} \sim 2 \times 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ GeV}^{-1} .$$

Models which allow self-interacting DM can be appealing because they can mitigate some tensions between observations of small-scale structures and predictions of the cold DM paradigm [24].

Figure 1.7: Possible range for the DM mass (also not particle hypothesis are included), and some notable candidates. Figure taken from [27].

- **Stability.**

Because the role of DM is fundamental both at the time of the CMB and now, it must be stable at least over the time scale of the age of the Universe. If it is not stable the constraints depend on the decay products. If they are visible they can effect the CMB spectrum and the following limits can be set [25]:

$$\tau_{\chi} \gtrsim 10^{25} - 10^{29} \text{ sec} .$$

Independently on the decay products a limit can be found from structures formation [26]:

$$\tau_{\chi} \gtrsim 10^{19} \text{ sec} .$$

1.3 Main Candidates

In the huge world of theoretical models, a vast horizon of possibilities can be found for particle DM, in the following only the main candidates are summarized. Beyond the ability to provide a solution to the problem under consideration, a good metric to evaluate a theoretical candidate is to see if it solves other open problems in the SM: this is a common feature of all the following hypotheses.

1.3.1 WIMPs: Weakly Interactive Massive Particles

There is no a clear definition of WIMP particle: for sure it does not refer to a particular candidate of a single theory but broadly, to a new elementary particle which interacts via gravity and any other force(s) which is as weak as or weaker than the weak nuclear force. Another important feature which defines a WIMP candidate is that it is produced thermally in the early Universe, similarly to the particles of the SM according to Big Bang cosmology. The mechanism is lightly reviewed the in the following section.

Freeze-Out DM Production in the Early Universe

The paradigm of thermal decoupling allows to make detailed predictions for observables in the early Universe, including the abundances of light elements and aspects related to the CMB [28]. For this reason it is quite natural to try to follow the same paradigm to infer the abundance of DM as a thermal relic from the early Universe. A detailed description of Freeze-Out mechanism can be found in [29], here we will just point out some key passages.

Suppose that the DM candidate is stable (or with lifetime longer than the age of the Universe $\tau_\chi \gg \tau_H$), with no relevant self-interaction. If we call B and \bar{B} the bath particles in which χ can annihilate, in this scenario the only number-changing interactions are:

$$\chi\bar{\chi} \longleftrightarrow B\bar{B} .$$

Considering T the temperature of the thermal bath, if $T > m_\chi$ DM is in thermal equilibrium, while for $T < m_\chi$ it decouples and its abundance starts to be exponentially Boltzmann suppressed. When the DM density becomes so small that the annihilation rate Γ_{ann} is slower than the expansion rate of the Universe H, $\Gamma_{\text{ann}} < H$, the thermal equilibrium can no longer be maintained and the WIMP abundance "froze out", resulting in the current relic abundance. Introducing the entropy density $s = 2\pi^2 g_s T^3/45$, where g_s is the effective number of degrees of freedom in entropy, using the conservation of entropy per co-moving volume we obtain:

$$Y_\chi \Big|_{T \leq T_{\text{fo}}} \equiv \frac{n_\chi}{s} \simeq \frac{\sqrt{\frac{8\pi^3}{90} g_\rho}}{\frac{2\pi^2}{45} g_s} \frac{T_{\text{fo}}^2}{T_{\text{fo}}^3 M_{\text{Pl}} \langle \sigma v \rangle} \simeq 0.4 \frac{1}{M_{\text{Pl}} \langle \sigma v \rangle T_{\text{fo}}} ,$$

where we used the fact that $g_\rho \simeq g_s \simeq \mathcal{O}(100)$ at high temperatures, when all the relativistic species are in equilibrium. One can show that $T_{\text{fo}} \simeq m_\chi/20$ [30]. Considering the quantities with zero subscript the ones at the present time, we can write the DM abundance obtained via Freeze-Out mechanism as:

$$\Omega_{\text{DM}} = \frac{\rho_\chi}{\rho_{\text{cr}}} = \frac{s_0 Y_{\chi,0} m_\chi}{3H_0^2/8\pi G} = 3 \cdot 10^{-27} \frac{\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}}{\langle \sigma v \rangle} .$$

In order to obtain the right relic abundance, the cross section has to be of the order of $\langle \sigma v \rangle \sim 3 \cdot 10^{-26} \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$. If we introduce a new particle with the typical weak interaction scale, the annihilation cross section is approximately: $\langle \sigma v \rangle \sim 10^{-26} \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$. The match between the two shows a very appealing coincidence, also known as the "WIMP miracle".

SUSY Candidates and the Neutralino

In the realm of WIMPs, particles coming from the spectrum of supersymmetric theories appear as one of the most natural candidates for DM. Supersymmetry (SUSY) is a possible extension of the SM as it addresses several theoretical issues like the fine-tuning problem of Higgs boson mass, the hierarchy problem, and the missing unification of gauge symmetries at high energies. A supersymmetric Lagrangian cannot be written limiting to the SM particles, so if we want to introduce this space-time symmetry we need to double the number of particles and define supermultiplets formed by the SM particle and its supersymmetric partner. They hold the same quantum numbers but their spins differ by a half-integer.

Figure 1.8: Tree-level Feynman diagrams for (left) neutralino-quark axial-vector spin-dependent (SD) elastic scattering interactions; (right) neutralino scalar spin-independent (SI) interactions. Figure taken from [30].

Initially, in this broad spectrum of new particles, at least three super-particles could constitute DM: the partners of neutrinos, named sneutrinos, the partners of gravitons named gravitinos, and a mixed states of the partners of neutral gauge bosons and the Higgs particle, named neutralinos. Sneutrinos are excluded as DM if their mass is set to give the correct relic density [31]. Considering gravitinos they interact only at the strength of gravity, which leads to hard problems for experimental searches [32]: so they are not a testable candidate for a direct search.

Taking into account the smallest possible field content in a supersymmetric theory necessary to give rise to all the SM, the so-called Minimal Supersymmetric Standard Model (MSSM), we have that binos (\tilde{B}), winos (\tilde{W}_3) and higgsinos ($\tilde{H}_1^0, \tilde{H}_2^0$) states mix into four Majorana fermionic mass eigenstates, called neutralinos. The four neutralinos are labeled as: $\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ (the lightest), $\tilde{\chi}_2^0, \tilde{\chi}_3^0$, and $\tilde{\chi}_4^0$ (the heaviest). The lightest one it is usually referred as the neutralino, $\chi \equiv \tilde{\chi}_1^0$.

The interesting processes for direct detection techniques are elastic scatterings with nucleons. WIMPs, which are nonrelativistic, generally couple to nuclei via an axial-vector (spin-dependent/SD) interaction or via a scalar and vector (spin-independent/SI) one. This important division for the direct detection was discussed the first time in [33] and the complete elastic-scattering is the sum of the two:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} \supset \mathcal{L}_{\text{SD}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{SI}} &= \mathcal{L}_{\text{SD}}^{\text{AV}} + (\mathcal{L}_{\text{SI}}^{\text{S}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{SI}}^{\text{V}}) \\ &= d_q \bar{\chi} \gamma^\mu \gamma_5 \chi \bar{q} \gamma^\mu \gamma_5 q + a_q \bar{\chi} \chi \bar{q} q + b_q \bar{\chi} \gamma_\mu \chi \bar{q} \gamma^\mu q, \end{aligned} \quad (1.7)$$

where d_q , a_q , and b_q are generic coupling while χ and q are the fields related to DM and a generic quark respectively. It is worthy of being remembered that the vector interaction with nuclei is present only for WIMPs which are not Majorana particles. The most important processes at the microscopic level are presented in figure 1.8.

For a full description of the theoretical framework and the cross sections of all different processes, please look [30, 34, 13, 35].

It is important to underline that the spin-independent contribution scales as the square of the number of nucleons A^2 , whereas the spin-dependent one is proportional to a function of the nuclear angular momentum, $(J + 1)/J$. For this reason, the SI contribution dominates for heavy targets ($A > 20$), which is the case for most experiments based on noble gases, such as argon and xenon.

1.3.2 Axions

An important open question in the SM is the so-called strong CP problem. The QCD Lagrangian has a CP violating term which is proportional to a scalar constant ϑ . At the

moment there are no good theoretical reasons in the SM to suppose something different from $\bar{\vartheta} \simeq \mathcal{O}(1)$, following the naturalness principle. One of the CP violating effects coming from that term in the Lagrangian is a non-vanishing electric dipole moment for the neutron with a predicted value of about:

$$d_n^{\text{th}} \simeq \bar{\vartheta} \times 10^{-16} \text{ e cm}. \quad (1.8)$$

Experiments searched for a neutron electric dipole moment, without finding it, and the most stringent current bound is:

$$d_n^{\text{exp}} \simeq 1.8 \times 10^{-26} \text{ e cm} \implies \bar{\vartheta} < 5 \times 10^{-11}. \quad (1.9)$$

The strong CP problem arises because this very small unexpected value for $\bar{\vartheta}$.

The Quinn-Peccei solution to the problem involves the introduction of a new global $U(1)_{\text{PQ}}$ symmetry, which when it is spontaneously broken, gives rise to the pseudo-Nambu-Goldstone boson known as axion $a(t, \mathbf{x})$ [36, 37]. In this framework we obtain $\bar{\vartheta} \propto a(t, \mathbf{x})$, and moreover the value $a = 0$ is energetically favourable so that $\bar{\vartheta}$ is dynamically and naturally driven to zero. Despite the fact that the axion comes from the breaking of a global symmetry, it has a small mass due to the $U(1)$ chiral anomaly. From perturbation theory one gets [38]:

$$m_a = 5.691(51) \left(\frac{10^9 \text{ GeV}}{f_a} \right) \text{ meV}, \quad (1.10)$$

where f_a is the axion decay constant. Depending on the value of f_a , axion masses can span roughly 12 orders of magnitudes: from $\sim 10^{-3}$ eV constrained by the CAST experiment down to $\sim 10^{-11}$ eV with the CASPER experiment [12]. The QCD axion can be easily introduced in theories BSM like SUSY, and it is a fixed prediction of string theory [39].

Axions can be produced in the early universe through a “standard” thermal production, but in that case, a hot DM candidate is found, which cannot fit the constraints coming from structure formation. For this reason a non-thermal production can be considered, for example the so-called misalignment mechanism. Different scenarios in this framework can be taken into account which can eventually significantly reduce the available mass range if we want axion to explain the whole observed DM, for a detailed review please see here [40].

1.3.3 Sterile Neutrinos

The fact that SM does not provide masses to (active) neutrinos is an open issue. A possible solution is the addition of new fermions, right-handed neutrinos, which are called sterile because they have no SM gauge interactions. The only interaction terms which involve sterile neutrinos are a Majorana mass term and a Yukawa coupling with the SM Higgs and the lepton doublets. This scenario gives the masses to the active neutrinos through the so-called see-saw mechanism [41]. If one or more sterile neutrinos have masses in the keV region, they can be long-lived enough to be a good warm DM candidate [42]. In general, they are produced in the early Universe via oscillations from active neutrinos: they never achieve thermal equilibrium, for this reason, they are in the set of non-thermal candidates. The relic density of sterile neutrinos depends on their masses and their mixing angles. A possible way to detect the existence of DM sterile

neutrinos is to look mono-energetic photons coming from the radiative decay channel $\nu_s \rightarrow \nu\gamma$ with energy $E_\gamma \simeq m_s/2$. Evidences of an X-ray line at ~ 3.5 KeV, which could be interpreted as decaying DM, was claimed, for example by the XMM-Newton satellite in several galaxy clusters [43]. However, the signal was not confirmed by the Suzaku [44] and Hitomi [45] missions.

1.3.4 Some Other Possibilities

In the previous subsections, the most famous particle candidates are quickly discussed. It is noteworthy to mention that another category of general DM particle candidates, called feebly interacting massive particles (FIMPs), has gained growing interest in recent years. FIMPs are produced non-thermally, but through the so-called freeze-in mechanism [46] and their detection as DM is particularly problematic as they interact with the SM sector extremely weakly. In fact, the usual Yukawa/gauge couplings are of the order of 10^{-11} [47].

Generally speaking, DM could be made up of a non-particle component such as the case of primordial black holes (PBHs) which have recently received particular attention and renewed interest [48]. Moreover, there are no experimental constraints that impose that the DM puzzle needs to be solved by a single new particle and it is important to bear in mind, therefore, that scenarios in which the abundance of DM is composed of a cocktail of particles are also allowed. Furthermore, as a non-gravitational effect caused by DM has not to be observed yet, some theories try to explain DM not with a candidate but as a case that requires an extension of general relativity. While the most simple and old model, i.e. the MODified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND), seems not to be the correct explanation [49], other more recent relativistic models, such as TeVeS may still be a possible solution [50] [51], also if they don't seem to explain all of the observational evidence for DM [52]. The present section that is going to end did not intend to mention all the possible options present in the literature, but only to stress how complex is the DM problem and how it is more open than ever.

CHAPTER 2

XENON: Direct Dark Matter Search

2.1 Introduction: Different Search Strategies

A decades-long, global worldwide experimental DM search is conducted in particular for WIMPs. However, efforts to detect other candidates, particularly axion/ALPs, have also grown considerably in recent years. Usually, there are three main experimental strategies, as can be seen in figure 2.1: direct detection, indirect detection, and collider searches.

In direct detection, signatures of processes that occurred in detectors involving DM are looked for. They include the scattering of a DM particle off a target in deep underground detectors, but also laboratory experiments for the axion. In the latter is primarily used the axion-photon conversion in the presence of a strong magnetic field, but also other complementary couplings to electron or nuclei [47].

Taking advantage of the fact that our Universe is full of DM, indirect searches look for excesses of SM particles coming from the galactic halo of the Milky Way and beyond. The hope is to find some signal above the usual astrophysical background, that could be eventually interpreted mainly as a product of residual DM annihilation, in particular in the thermal DM paradigm. This is pursued using charged cosmic rays experiments, neutrino, gamma ray, and x ray telescopes [53].

In collider searches, for instance at LHC, the investigation is focused on the production of a DM pair in a collision. As the hypothetical pairs will propagate without leaving any trace in the detector, being electrically neutral and cosmologically stable, their presence can be inferred from missing energy and momentum [54].

Since the present thesis concerns direct detection with the XENONnT experiment,

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of the WIMPs detection channels. As currently there is no certainty of how the interactions occur, the portal is represented as a black box. Figure taken from [55].

the other strategies will not be further discussed. Nevertheless, it is worth highlighting two important aspects of why direct detection is to be preferred, in principle, over the other two methods. Concerning indirect detection it is really difficult, once a hypothetical signal has been identified, to decouple the astronomical uncertainties, which also cannot be directly accessed and studied. Regarding the collider searches, new particles with the right properties may be detected, however, no assurance could be given that this component is the one that fills the Universe. Nevertheless, it must be emphasised that the eventual first detection of DM will likely be a first leap in its study and this process surely will require employing a multi-channel and multi-messenger approach, combining information from all the strategies.

2.2 Underground Searches for WIMPs: Detection Idea

As it is discussed in subsection 1.1.1, our galaxy is most likely embedded in a large spherical DM halo, which contrarily from the stellar galactic disk does not rotate and here is supposed to be made by WIMP particles. As the Earth moves through it, we should experience a headwind of them that appears to come from the Cygnus constellation.

As can be seen in figure 2.2, there are two main components that have an impact on the WIMP-wind: the rotation of the Sun around the centre of the galaxy and the one of the Earth around the Sun. The results showed in direct detection experiments usually assume that DM particles are distributed in an isotropic and isothermal sphere with a truncated Maxwellian velocity distribution. Its variance σ_0 is defined by the local standard of rest at the location of the Sun $|\vec{v}_0| = \sqrt{2}\sigma_0$. Introducing the Sun's peculiar velocity, \vec{v}_\odot , the Earth's velocity relative to the Sun, \vec{v}_\oplus , the lab-frame WIMP velocity, \vec{v}_{lab} , ρ_χ and m_χ the local WIMP density and the WIMP mass, the distribution reads [57]:

Figure 2.2: Schematic representation of the motions of the Earth through the hypothetical WIMP wind. Figure taken from [56].

$$f(\vec{v}_{\text{gal}}) \propto \frac{\rho_{\chi}}{m_{\chi}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} |\vec{v}_{\text{gal}}|^2 / \sigma_0^2\right) \Theta(v_{\text{esc}} - |\vec{v}_{\text{gal}}|), \quad (2.1)$$

$$\vec{v}_{\text{gal}} = \vec{v}_{\text{lab}} + (\vec{v}_0 + \vec{v}_{\odot} + \vec{v}_{\oplus}(t)), \quad (2.2)$$

where the $\Theta(x)$ is the Heaviside step function, used to truncate values larger than the escape velocity, related to the gravitational potential of the galaxy.

Parameter	Value	Reference
ρ_{χ}	0.3 [GeV/c ² /cm ³]	[58]
v_{esc}	544 [km/s]	[59]
$\langle \vec{v}_{\oplus} \rangle$	29.8 [km/s]	[60]
\vec{v}_{\odot}	(11.1, 12.2, 7.3) [km/s]	[61]
\vec{v}_0	(0, 238, 0) [km/s]	[62, 63]

Table 2.1: Some selected values of the Standard Halo Model.

To have an idea of what experiments are looking for, an approximate estimation of the size of the flux of DM particles expected on the Earth is performed in the following. From the local energy density and its relation with the number density, the incoming flux reads:

$$\varphi_{\chi} = n_{\chi} v_{\chi} = \frac{\rho_{\chi}}{m_{\chi}} v_{\chi}. \quad (2.3)$$

We can report a numerical estimation with the typical used symbolic value for the WIMP mass (50 GeV/c²), which is in general model-dependent:

$$\varphi_{\chi}|_{m_{\chi}=50\text{GeV}} \simeq 1.3 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}. \quad (2.4)$$

Just for a comparison, the total flux of the solar neutrinos is $\varphi_{\nu, \text{sun}} \simeq 6.54 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ [64] and their detection was really tough.

As WIMPs have no electric charge, the interaction with ordinary matter consists of an elastic scatter with an atomic nucleus. The momentum transfer in the scattering can give rise to a nuclear recoil (NR), which might be detectable. The differential rate for a detector with mass M reads [13]:

$$\frac{dR}{dE_{\text{nr}}} = \frac{\rho_{\chi} M}{m_{\text{N}} m_{\chi}} \int_{v_{\text{min}}}^{v_{\text{esc}}} v f(v) \frac{d\sigma}{dE_{\text{nr}}}(v, E_{\text{nr}}) dv, \quad (2.5)$$

where E_{nr} is the NR energy, σ the cross section for the interaction, m_{N} the target nucleus and v_{min} the minimal velocity necessary for a WIMP to induce a nuclear recoil of energy E_{nr} . Considering a single scattering, from the kinematics of the elastic collision one can obtain that the recoil energy results in:

$$E_{\text{R}} = 2 \left(\frac{m_{\chi} m_{\text{N}}}{m_{\chi} + m_{\text{N}}} \right)^2 \frac{v_{\chi}^2}{m_{\text{N}}} \cos^2 \vartheta, \quad (2.6)$$

with v_{χ} the WIMP particle velocity, m_{χ} its mass, m_{N} the mass of the nuclear target and ϑ its final state angle. Running an experiment for a total time T , the number of observed events reads:

$$N = T \int_{E_{\text{low}}}^{E_{\text{high}}} dE_{\text{nr}} \varepsilon(E_{\text{nr}}) \frac{dR}{dE_{\text{nr}}}, \quad (2.7)$$

where the detector efficiency ε usually varies with the deposited energy.

The velocity of the Earth moving through the DM halo slightly changes during the year and this has an impact on the differential rate (see 2.5). Knowing that the inclination angle measured between the Earth's orbit and the galactic plane is $\vartheta \simeq 60^\circ$, the velocity of the Earth moving through the DM halo can be written as:

$$v_E = v_\odot + v_\oplus \cos(\vartheta) \cos[\omega(t - t_0)], \quad (2.8)$$

where the angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi/T$ is defined by $T = 1$ y and the phase is fixed to $t_0 = \text{June } 2^{\text{nd}}$ when v_E is maximum. Only a very small fraction $\mathcal{O}(1\% - 10\%)$ of the total DM scattering rate undergoes a modulation phenomenon [65]. In case a future signal attributable to WIMP particles will be found, an annual modulation would be a powerful argument to support it.

2.2.1 Liquid Xenon as a Detection Medium

Different motivations lead to the choice of liquefied noble gas, in particular liquid xenon (LXe) and liquid argon (LAr) to build a DM detector. First of all, they are excellent scintillators and very good ionizers in response to the passage of radiation, this is a key feature to build a dual-phase time projection chamber (TPC) as we will describe later. They are in the gaseous state at the standard temperature and pressure (STP), for this reason working at cryogenics temperature is necessary in order to use them in the liquid phase. In the following table, a quick summary of some of the most important features of the two noble gas is reported.

Element	Xenon	Argon
Atomic Number Z	54	18
Atomic mass A	131.3	40.0
Boiling Point T_b [K]	165.0	87.3
Liquid Density @ T_b [g/cm ³]	2.94	1.40
Fraction in Earth's Atmosphere [ppm]	0.09	9340
Price	\$\$\$\$	\$
Scintillator	✓	✓
$W_{\text{ph}}(\alpha, \beta)$ [eV]	17.9 / 21.6	27.1 / 24.4
Scintillation Wavelength [nm]	174.8	128.1
Ionizer	✓	✓
$W_{e\text{-ion}}$ [eV]	13.6	23.6

Table 2.2: Selected properties of LXe and LAr, noble gases usually used as target material for direct detection of WIMPs. W_{ph} and $W_{e\text{-ion}}$ are the mean energies required to create a scintillation photon and an electron-ion pair respectively. Values taken from [66, 67, 68, 69].

The choice of LXe as active target implies several advantages:

1. **Cross section:** it has the higher mass number, this is fundamental because as described in section 1.3.1 for the dominant spin-independent contribution holds: $\sigma^{\text{IN}} \propto A^2$.
2. **Stability:** the almost absence (see ^{136}Xe and ^{124}Xe [70]) of unstable isotopes minimizes internal background, instead in $^{\text{nat}}\text{Ar}$ the radioactive isotope ^{39}Ar is

present, with an activity of $\simeq 1\text{Bq/kg}$, which is necessary to remove in order to use it.

3. **Stopping power:** the higher density shown in [table 2.2](#) allows a better self-shielding power against external background sources with the definition of a fiducial volume.
4. **Odd isotopes:** roughly $\simeq 47.6\%$ of the natural abundance of Xe has nonzero spin (^{129}Xe (spin 1/2) and ^{131}Xe (spin 3/2)), this allows a spin-dependent analysis which could be very useful for the understanding of DM nature.
5. **Ionization/Light yield:** as can be read in [table 2.2](#) the effective ionization and scintillation potentials are lower so that, given the same amount of energy deposited due to an interaction, the number of photons and electrons produced is larger.
6. **Cryogenic:** LXe is less demanding from the cryogenic point of view in order to use it in the liquid phase.

One of the most serious reasons that have limited the use of LXe in the past is the high cost, in fact, GXe constitutes $\simeq 1$ part over 10^7 of Earth's atmosphere and it is extracted from air by the gas industry using separation plants. Its cost can vary usually in the interval $(1\text{k} \div 2\text{k}) \text{€}/\text{kg}$. The price is still manageable and it allows to scale up to large target mass, which is not the case for other good detection materials such as semiconductors.

2.2.2 Signal Generation: Scintillation and Ionization

The energy deposited by the passage of a particle in LXe is converted into ionization, excitations and free electrons with kinetic energy lower than the first excited state (subexcitation electrons).

Calling N_i the electron-ion pairs, N_{ex} the excited atoms and E_0 the deposited energy in the material the Platzman balance equation holds [71]:

$$E_0 = N_i E_i + N_{\text{ex}} E_x + N_i \varepsilon, \quad (2.9)$$

where E_i and E_x are the average energies needed to ionize and excite an atom respectively, while ε is the average kinetic energy of subexcitation electrons.

Given an amount of absorbed energy E_0 , the conversion efficiency to a measurable signal is determined by the W -value, the average energy required to produce an electron-ion pair, and by W_{ph} , the average energy required to produce a scintillation photon.

$$W = \frac{E_0}{N_i} = E_i + E_x \frac{N_{\text{ex}}}{N_i} + \varepsilon, \quad (2.10)$$

$$W_{\text{ph}} = \frac{E_0}{N_{\text{ex}} + N_i} = \frac{W}{N_{\text{ex}}/N_i + 1}. \quad (2.11)$$

In general, the W -value in the liquid phase is smaller than in the gaseous phase [72].

The Processes

The luminescence phenomenon in liquids or solids is called scintillation and it consists in the emission of photons from an atom in order to reach a minimum energy configuration. The production of a scintillation photon in a noble gas, here we refer to the specific case of Xe, can occur both as a result of an excitation Xe^* and of an ionization Xe^+ . In both processes, there is the production of an excited dimer Xe_2^* , by collision, which, with the emission of a vacuum-ultraviolet (VUV) photons, de-excite to a dissociated ground state.

Excitation
$E_0 \rightarrow \text{Xe}^*$ $\text{Xe}^* + \text{Xe} + \text{Xe} \rightarrow \text{Xe}_2^* + \text{Xe}$ $\text{Xe}_2^* \rightarrow 2\text{Xe} + \gamma$
Ionization
$E_0 \rightarrow \text{Xe}^+ + e^-$ $\text{Xe}^+ + \text{Xe} \rightarrow \text{Xe}_2^+$ $\text{Xe}_2^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{Xe}^{**} + \text{Xe}$ $\text{Xe}^{**} \rightarrow \text{Xe}^* + \text{heat}$ $\text{Xe}^* + \text{Xe} + \text{Xe} \rightarrow \text{Xe}_2^* + \text{Xe}$ $\text{Xe}_2^* \rightarrow 2\text{Xe} + \gamma$

The scintillation light emitted in case of liquid xenon has a wavelength [68]:

$$\lambda_{\gamma}^{\text{LXe}} = (174.8 \pm 0.1(\text{stat.}) \pm 0.1(\text{syst.}) \text{ nm}),$$

this value is larger w.r.t. the ones for LAr ($\simeq 125$ nm) or LNe ($\simeq 78$ nm) and allows light detection without the usage of a wavelength shifter.

Liquid neon, argon and xenon emit scintillation light with two decay components (fast and slow) due to de-excitation of singlet and triplet states of the excited dimer $\text{Xe}_2^* \rightarrow 2\text{Xe} + \gamma$. The behaviour in time of the number of emitted gammas, a.k.a. light response, reads:

$$N(t) = \frac{f_s}{\tau_s} \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_s}\right) + \frac{f_t}{\tau_t} \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_t}\right). \quad (2.12)$$

The decay time can vary under intense electric fields, in case of LXe with a 4 kV/cm electric field, the decay times after the interaction of relativistic electrons with xenon atoms are: $\tau_s = (2.2 \pm 0.3)$ ns from the singlet states and $\tau_t = (27 \pm 1)$ ns from triplet ones [72].

The difference in the scintillation pulse decay shape can in principle be used for particle identification, however in the case of LXe due to the difference of only a few nanoseconds, this is currently not implemented, while it is a feasible strategy in the case of LAr.

2.2.3 Detection Principle of a Double Phase TPC

Dual-phase (liquid and gaseous) TPC, like the one that can be seen in figure 2.3, are the kind of detectors proposed by the XENON collaboration during the years to directly detect WIMP particles.

Figure 2.3: Schematic view of the working principle of XENONnT as an example of double phase TPC.

In case a particle deposits energy in the active volume, through interactions, it creates ionization electrons and prompt scintillation photons. The kind of interaction depends on the nature of the incoming particle: neutrons, WIMP particles and neutrinos, scattering with the xenon nuclei, will induce a nuclear recoil (NR), while γ rays, electrons and neutrinos can interact with atomic electrons causing an electron recoil (ER) as is shown in figure 2.4.

Scintillation photons form the primary **S1** signal, they are emitted isotropically and detected by the two arrays of light detectors, photomultiplier tubes (PMTs), placed at the top and the bottom of the TPC. The active region of the TPC is enclosed by PTFE (TeflonTM) reflector panels in order to increase the detection of the produced photons. The ionization electrons are drifted in LXe by an external electric field $\vec{E}_{\text{drift}} \simeq \mathcal{O}(10^2 \text{ V/cm})$ and they are extracted from the liquid to the gas by means of a more intense extraction electric field $\vec{E}_{\text{extraction}} \simeq \mathcal{O}(10^4 \text{ V/cm})$ generated between the grounded gate and the positively biased anode. The following acceleration of the electrons determines a multiplication process and then they collide with xenon nuclei and excite Xe atoms. A light signal proportional to the number of ionization electrons is isotropically generated, which is known as secondary **S2** signal. For each electron,

Figure 2.4: Different interactions that can happen in the target volume of the TPC.

the effective charge gain factor is of the order of $\mathcal{O}(10 - 40)$ PE/e⁻, where PE are the photoelectrons generated from the PMT photocathode.

In the following table some designed parameters of the XENONnT detector are reported.

Designed Detector Parameter	Values [unit]
LXe Target Mass	5.9 [T]
Radius (Active Volume)	66.4 [cm]
Depth (Active Volume)	148.5 [cm]
Distance Gate-Anode	8 [mm]
# PMTs Top	253
# PMTs Bottom	241
\vec{E}_{drift}	200 [V/cm]
$\vec{E}_{\text{extraction}}$	8 [kV/cm]

Table 2.3: Some selected designed parameters of the XENONnT experiment. Values taken from [70].

Light Absorption

An important requirement for scintillators is that they should be transparent to their scintillation light. This is fulfilled by LXe as the de-excitation to the dissociative ground is from an excited dimer Xe_2^* and not from an excited atom Xe^* . The small number of impurities $< \mathcal{O}(1 \text{ ppb})$ and the absorption at the detector surfaces may reduce the number of photons that arrive at the PMTs. The reduction in intensity of the initial light produced I_0 for a given optical path \vec{l} can be described as:

$$I(x) = I_0 e^{-|\vec{l}|/\lambda_{\text{abs}}}, \quad (2.13)$$

where λ_{abs} is the absorption length, which is inversely proportional to the number of impurities in the LXe (see next subsection). Along their path, photons can undergo Rayleigh scattering, which does not cause a significant loss of signal, but it changes the direction of propagation. As the wavelength of light is much larger than Xe atom diameter, then Mie scattering is not observed.

Optical Property	Values [unit]
λ_{abs}	> 50 [m]
λ_{sca}	35 [cm]
Refractive Index LXe (GXe)	1.69 (1)

Table 2.4: Some selected optical properties in the case of XENONnT experiment. Values tuned from [70].

In the case of dual-phase TPC detectors, total reflection of photons at the LXe/GXe interface can occur.

Electron Transport

At very low velocities ($\beta \lesssim 0.01$) the energy transferred to atoms via inelastic collisions is not described by the Bethe-Bloch equation, but by Lindhard's stopping power theory

Figure 2.5: Longitudinal and transverse diffusion coefficient as a function of the drift field \vec{E}_{drift} in the case of LXe. Plot taken from [76].

[73]. The smallest W-value that characterizes LXe (see table 2.2) among the other noble liquids, guarantees a considerable production of electrons.

Due to thermal motion, the produced electron cloud will spread during the motion caused by the \vec{E}_{drift} . In presence of an external electric field, the net effect is different in the direction longitudinal (L) and transverse (T) to the field:

$$\sigma_{T/L}^2 = 2 D_{T/L} t_{\text{drift}}. \quad (2.14)$$

For $E_{\text{drift}} > 10^3$ V/cm it was measured that $D_L \simeq 0.1 D_T$, as is shown in figure 2.5. However, it seems that this ratio no longer holds for lower values of E_{drift} [74, 75].

Another fundamental and detrimental process, which the charge signal can undergo during the drift is **electron attachment**, which causes a decrease in the electron concentration $[e]$. Considering $[X]_i$, the concentration of the impurity i , and K_{S_i} its attachment rate constant, the following relationship holds:

$$[e(t)] = [e(0)] e^{-(\sum_i K_{S_i} [X]_i) t} = [e(0)] e^{-t/\tau_{e^-}}, \quad (2.15)$$

where the **electron lifetime** τ_{e^-} is introduced and it represents the mean free time after which an electrons is captured by an impurity. Another quantity often used to describe this phenomenon is the electron attenuation length :

$$\lambda_{\text{att}} = \mu E_{\text{drift}} \tau_{e^-}. \quad (2.16)$$

where μ is the electron mobility. To obtain $\lambda_{\text{att}} \gtrsim 1$ m is required a concentration of impurities lower than 1 ppb O_2 -equivalent level. The main electronegative impurities in LXe experiments are oxygen (O_2), water (H_2O) and carbon dioxide (CO_2).

Xe atoms, having a large atomic size, can be polarized by excess electrons and this generates an attractive force among them. The effect is stronger in the liquid phase than in the gas, due to the dielectric constant difference.

As a consequence, a quasi-free electron during the drift has ground state energy lower in the liquid than in the gas, forming a potential barrier of $E_{\text{barrier}} \in (0.6 - 0.85)$ eV at the liquid-gas interface.

Due to the presence of the barrier, electrons need to be accelerated to overcome it and for this reason the grounded gate is placed not at the interface, but a little below

Figure 2.6: Extraction efficiency for different values of $\vec{E}_{\text{extraction}}$ present in the liquid for experiments which use Xe. Plot taken from [77].

in the liquid phase. The value of $\vec{E}_{\text{extraction}} \simeq 8 \text{ kV/cm}$ present in the XENONnT experiment ensure an electron extraction efficiency close to one (see figure 2.6).

2.2.4 Discriminating Electronic and Nuclear Recoils

The measure of both scintillation photons (S1) and ionization electrons (S2) allows to distinguish ER from NR. Particles with different stopping power dE/dx , have different S2/S1 ratios and this can be exploited for discrimination.

Sources of electron recoil, such as gamma and electrons, deposit energy along their trajectory and having a rather large scattering length they generate a low ionisation density.

Hypothetical WIMPs and neutrons predominantly lose their energy in recoils with Xe nuclei with a larger ionisation density. It implies a larger recombination probability with a reduced S2 signal and larger S1, thus a lower S2/S1 ratio. The anticorrelation between ionization and scintillation signals was experimentally observed [78].

In light of the previous lines, the ratio S2/S1 is a successful strategy to discriminate ER from NR events:

$$\left(\frac{S2}{S1}\right)_{\text{ER}} \gg \left(\frac{S2}{S1}\right)_{\text{NR}}. \quad (2.17)$$

Gammas and electrons emitters are usually used to calibrate the detector response to ER, while neutrons sources are adopted for NR events. For the calibration of XENON1T experiment, β decays of ^{212}Pb from a ^{220}Rn source were exploited to calibrate ER events, while for NR events $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ (neutron source) was used.

The analysis strategy of XENON1T, however, did not apply a hard cut to reject ER events, but, with a profile likelihood treatment, it exploited the full information of the ER and NR distributions in the (S1, S2) space [79]. In NR signals a portion of the deposited energy cannot be detected as it is transferred as kinetic energy to the surrounding atoms and lost as heat. This implies for NR that the light/charge yield for a given energy is smaller than the one for ER.

Figure 2.7: Comparison of ER and NR calibration data to illustrate discrimination capability between ER and NR events in (S1, S2) space in XENON1T detector. Both the axes are corrected for spatial effects in the TPC, hence the c prefix, while only the bottom PMT array is used for the S2 signal, hence the b subscript. Plot taken from [77].

2.2.5 Energy Reconstruction

The reconstruction of the energy of the event is a key step in order to achieve particle identification (PID). In dual-phase Xenon TPC there are two procedures depending on whether the event has been classified as ER or NR (see subsection 2.2.4). The two detected signals, S1 and S2, are affected by significant inefficiencies and position dependent effects. This is the reason why they must be corrected to get the reconstructed number of emitted photons and electrons. A light collection efficiency (LCE) map is applied to S1 signal to take into account detector geometrical efficiencies and PMTs quantum efficiencies. This correction map is obtained from the 41.5 keV line of the gaseous metastable krypton isotope $^{83\text{m}}\text{Kr}$ injected in the TPC in calibration runs, obtaining an approximate homogeneous distribution of sources in the entire volume after the correction for each position.

The proportional scintillation signal S2 needs to be corrected both for its LCE map and for the electron lifetime, as during the drift impurities and recombinations reduce the charge signal exponentially with the z position of the event. The electron lifetime τ_e is measured in calibration runs by fitting the exponential decay of S2 signal intensity from ER calibration sources as a function of the z position. Two common choices for the sources are α particles from ^{222}Rn and monoenergetic gammas from $^{83\text{m}}\text{Kr}$.

After the application of those corrections to both S1 and S2 signals, the corrected **cS1** and **cS2** are obtained.

Combined Energy Scale for ER

The energy deposited by ERs is converted into a measurable signal, without significant energy loss in heat, in contrast with NRs. For historical reasons this loss is also called "quenching effect", even if it does not happen any quenching by impurities or

ionization density, but quanta are not being created from the beginning. Fluctuations in ionization and scintillation are anticorrelated, for this reason, a linear energy scale can be constructed, in which cancellation of the recombination fluctuations is obtained by adding the two signals. This energy scale is called combined energy scale (CES) and it is independent from the applied electric fields, while individual scintillation and ionization yield depend on it. Simplifying Platzman equation can be defined a mean work function $W = 13.7 \pm 0.2 \text{ eV}$ [80] to produce one quanta (photon or electron) in LXe. This was shown to be as effective as defining two distinct work functions for successfully explaining experimental results and it causes no loss of generality [81, 82].

Then the CES for ERs reads:

$$E = W \cdot (n_\gamma + n_{e^-}), \quad (2.18)$$

where n_γ and n_{e^-} are the number of emitted photons and electrons. To link it to measurable quantities we introduce detector response parameters, which depend only on detector and not on energy source and the drift field:

1. g_1 : photon detection efficiency, also called primary scintillation gain. It is the number of observed photoelectrons per photon and takes into account the light collection efficiency (LCE) and the PMT quantum efficiency.

$$g_1 = \frac{cS1}{n_\gamma}. \quad (2.19)$$

2. g_2 : electron detection efficiency, also called secondary scintillation gain. It is the number of observed photoelectrons per electron and takes into account the extraction efficiency and the electron multiplication due a strong electric field.

$$g_2 = \frac{cS2_b}{n_{e^-}}. \quad (2.20)$$

Figure 2.8: Spectrum of ^{137}Cs at 662 keV with three different energy reconstruction approaches. Using S1-only the resolution is 12.5%, for S2-only 6.5%, and 2.3 % for the CES where the anticorrelation between charge and light signal is exploited. Plot taken from [83].

Figure 2.9: Doke plot: anticorrelation between the measured light yield (LY) and charge yield (QY) using monoenergetic lines. The single-site (SS) and for multi-site (MS) interactions have different values at a given energy due to the energy dependent ion-electron recombination processes. Plot taken from [85].

$cS2_b$ refers to the fraction of the total $cS2$ collected in the bottom array. Currently, it is preferred, as it is more homogeneously distributed over the entire bottom array area and the small scale distortions have less significant impact. The fraction of the total S2 signal measured by the bottom PMT array in case of XENON1T is $(37 \pm 2) \%$ [84]. The proportional photons collected on the top, instead, are mainly detected by few PMTs and eventual non operational PMTs can cause important variations in the detection efficiency. It follows that the CES for ERs can be rewritten as:

$$E = W \cdot \left(\frac{cS1}{g_1} + \frac{cS2_b}{g_2} \right). \quad (2.21)$$

The improvement achieved using CES looks clear from figure 2.8.

To calibrate the energy scale, obtaining the value of g_1 and g_2 , sources producing monoenergetic lines of known energy or background are deployed as shown and described in figure 2.9.

In XENON1T experiment the energy resolution was parameterized fitting all the identified peaks in the ER spectrum obtaining [85]:

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{E} = \frac{31.3 \pm 0.7}{\sqrt{E [\text{keV}]}} + (0.17 \pm 0.02) [\text{keV}]. \quad (2.22)$$

Equivalent Energy for NR

For NRs a not negligible quantity of energy is lost into heat (atomic motion) instead of observable quanta, resulting in a Lindhard factor of 0.1 - 0.2 in LXe [86]. The reconstruction of NR energy, or nuclear recoil equivalent energy E_{nr} , is usually obtained

from signal S1:

$$E_{\text{nr}} = \frac{S1}{L_{y,\text{er}}} \frac{1}{\mathcal{L}_{\text{eff}}} \frac{S_{\text{er}}}{S_{\text{nr}}}, \quad (2.23)$$

where S_{er} and S_{nr} are the scintillation light field quenching factors for ERs and NRs respectively, $L_{y,\text{er}}$ is the light yield and \mathcal{L}_{eff} is the relative scintillation efficiency. In the experiment XENON100 for instance, the following values are obtained: $L_{y,\text{er}} = (2.20 \pm 0.09) \text{ PE/keV}$, $S_{\text{er}} = 0.58$ and $S_{\text{nr}} = 0.95$ [87].

2.3 XENONnT Experiment

The XENONnT experiment is the current version of the dual-phase TPC built by the XENON collaboration, a schematic view can be seen in figure 2.11. The experiment is hosted in the Hall B of the Laboratori Nazionali del Gran Sasso (LNGS), under 3600 meters-water-equivalent mountain rock.

An important goal is to shield the LXe target mass against external backgrounds, this is the reason why the experiment is placed underground and 3 nested detectors are built: the muon veto, the neutron veto and the TPC. At LNGS the flux of cosmic muons with a mean energy of $\langle E_{\mu\pm} \rangle \simeq 270 \text{ GeV}$ [88] is reduced by a factor $\sim 10^{-6}$ w.r.t. the ground with a reduced value of $(3.432 \pm 0.003) \cdot 10^4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [89].

The Cherenkov muon veto is formed by a tank (diameter of 9.6 m and a height of 10.2 m) filled with ultrapure water so that it acts as a passive shield and a detector of those charged particles which fulfil the Cherenkov threshold. It can identify the cosmogenic muons and tag the muon-induced neutrons by detecting showers originating from muon interactions outside the water. It is equipped with 84 PMTs (Hamamatsu R5912ASSY) with diameter of 20.32 cm, has a trigger rate of $\simeq 0.35 \text{ Hz}$, a detection efficiency of $(99.78 \pm 0.05) \%$ for muons and $(71.4 \pm 0.5) \%$ for showers of secondary particles [91].

	XENON10	XENON100	XENON1T	XENONnT	DARWIN
operation	2005-2007	2008-2016	2012-2018	2020-2025	2027–
total mass	15 kg	161 kg	3200 kg	8400 kg	50 tonnes
detector radius	15 cm	30 cm	96 cm	150 cm	260 cm
WIMP σ	$\sim 10^{-43} \text{ cm}^2$	$\sim 10^{-45} \text{ cm}^2$	$\sim 10^{-47} \text{ cm}^2$	$\sim 10^{-48} \text{ cm}^2$	$\sim 10^{-49} \text{ cm}^2$

Figure 2.10: Evolution of dual-phase TPC experiments built by the XENON collaboration. The hardest challenge which limits the increase of the target mass is the fulfilling of the ultra-low background requirement.

Figure 2.11: Representation of XENONnT experiment with all its subsystems [90].

The neutron veto is a new detector in XENONnT and it is formed by an octagonal structure with a height of 3 m and an apothem of 2 m filled with Gd-doped ultrapure water at 0.2 % mass concentration. The presence of gadolinium with its high cross-section for neutron capture allows to absorb radiogenic neutrons and to detect them with the consequent emission of a γ ray cascades. Neutron background is particularly dangerous, as the interaction in the TPC is very similar to the NR caused by WIMPs particles. In the neutron veto, 120 PMTs (Hamamatsu R5912ASSY) with a diameter of 20.32 cm are installed, the neutron tagging efficiency is $\simeq 85$ % with NR background suppression of a factor 6 [92].

The active region of TPC is enclosed by 24 PTFE (TeflonTM) reflector panels, the same material is also used to fill the space between PMT windows in both the arrays. They are used in order to maximize the light collection efficiency, to optically separates the active region of the TPC from the outside and to insulate the active region. Their surfaces are treated with diamond polished to optimize the reflectivity > 99 % for $\lambda = 174.8$ nm (VUV) light. An important issue introduced by PTFE is that they contribute to neutron background. Considering the chemical formula of TeflonTM $(C_2F_4)_n$, one finds ^{nat}F which has one stable isotope (^{19}F) which has a high neutron emission yield in (α, n) reactions with the release of MeV neutrons. To tag those events is crucial the presence of the neutron veto, in fact, after having interacted one or more times inside the fiducial volume, the emitted neutron goes outside of the TPC, it thermalizes and is captured by gadolinium and its track can be identified. An accurate description of all the subsystems present in the service building that can be seen in the right part of figure 2.11 is beyond the scope for the continuation of the present work, for the sake of completeness in the following their tasks will be just mentioned.

To remove the intrinsic contamination of ^{nat}Kr and ^{222}Rn , homogeneously distributed inside the LXe, two different distillation columns are installed [93]. They deploy the differences of vapour pressure among the considered elements and they are fundamental to achieve the purity requirements necessary to obtain the desired sensitivity [70].

The purification systems of LXe and GXe based on copper filters are used to reduce lower than 1 ppb O_2 -equivalent level the electronegative impurities to maintain an electron lifetime $\tau_{e^-} > 1$ ms. Thanks to an apparatus based on liquid nitrogen the cryogenics system allows to liquefy the GXe and maintain the operating conditions of $T_{exp} \simeq -96^\circ C$ and $p_{exp} \simeq 2$ bar pressure in the experiment. The XENONnT TPC is inside a double-walled cryostat to block convective heat transfer. The two storage

vessels, ReStoX I (capacity 7.6 t) and ReStoX II (capacity 10 t), can store Xe either in gas or liquid phase under high purity conditions.

2.4 Projected Sensitivity

A signal from a WIMP particle is expected to interact only one time in the NR band, due to the low cross section. Even if the discrimination between ERs and NRs can be successfully achieved (see subsection 2.2.4) a meticulous understanding of ER background sources is required, as there could be statistical leakage of the ER population, producing events indistinguishable from WIMPs. A complete survey of the sources of background is beyond the scope of this work (see [70] for an overview). Firstly, considering the sources of background, we can distinguish among internal, intrinsic and external backgrounds. The energy range of interest (energy ROI) for ER background is selected between (1, 13) keV. The internal ER background is related to processes due to traces of radioactive isotopes in the detector components and to limit it all the material used to build the experiment are selected and screened through a scrupulous radioassay program [94, 95]. Among internal ER background sources, there are the γ s emitted in the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decays chains and from the decay of ^{60}Co , ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs . To suppress those kinds of backgrounds a fiducial volume of 4 t of LXe out of a total of 5.9 t is selected, using the outer LXe layer as a shield. The intrinsic ER background mainly consist in xenon-intrinsic contamination such as ^{222}Rn , ^{85}Kr and the unstable xenon isotopes ^{135}Xe and ^{124}Xe .

Concerning background sources for NR, the energy ROI is selected between (4, 50) keV. Radiogenic neutrons produced through spontaneous emission and (α, n) reactions in detector materials, in particular due to the presence of PTFE, are sources of internal NR background. The muon-induced neutrons, caused by the interactions with the rocks and materials surrounding the detector are a source of external NR background. Neutrino interaction from solar, atmospheric and diffuse supernova (DNS) neutrinos of intrinsic NR background, as they are uniformly distributed inside the detector. Neutrinos contribute to the NR background also through CE ν NS, coherent elastic neutrino-nucleus scattering. A quantitative representation of what was quickly

Figure 2.12: Simulated energy spectra of the ER (left) and NR (right) backgrounds of the XENONnT experiment in the 4 t fiducial volume. Plot taken from [70].

Figure 2.13: (Left) median 90% CL exclusion limit (black solid line) for the sensitivity to the spin-independent WIMP-nucleon cross section with a 20 t y exposure. The green band correspond to 1σ while the yellow to 2σ . (Right) Sensitivity as a function of exposure in 4 t fiducial mass for an hypothetical 50 GeV/c^2 WIMP particle. Plot taken from [70].

summarized can be found in figure 2.12.

Assuming the standard model of the dark matter halo (section 2.2) the sensitivity to the spin-independent WIMP-nucleon cross section can be obtained (see figure 2.14). At light masses, the sensitivity drastically worsens due to detector threshold effects. At large mass, the behaviour is determined by the suppression in the number density which causes the linear trend with the WIMP mass. In figure 2.14 can be see how the plots shown in figure 2.14 vary due to changes in the experimental conditions.

Figure 2.14: General representation of how plots in figure 2.13 vary due to changes in the detector design or properties. Illustration taken from [96].

CHAPTER 3

Position Reconstruction in XENONnT

Event reconstruction is the key to exploit the potential of a particle physics experiment. Raw data collected in the different detector components are combined to reconstruct the interaction of particles in the detector. Concretely, in the XENONnT experiment, event reconstruction involves determining the three dimensional position, (x,y,z) , of a particle with the target material, the deposited energy (see [subsection 2.2.5](#)), and other background rejection parameters such as the probability of an event to be an ER or a NR.

3.1 Motivation

Reconstructing the three-dimensional spatial position of each recoil event inside the TPC of XENONnT is crucial to define the fiducial volume, to correct the signal and to reject external background.

3.1.1 Signal Corrections

The measured S1 and S2 signals depend on the event location, as the detector's response is not uniform in space. All the corrections, data-driven maps, and formulas shown in this section that depend on (x,y,z) require an accurate position reconstruction.

Correction to S1 Signal

Given a deposited energy, E_0 , in the sensitive volume, different effects impact the light yield, LY, which is defined as $S1/E_0$. First of all, the photon yield, (PY), which is the the number of photons produced per deposited energy, depends on E_0 and the drift field \vec{E}_{drift} , as the latter modifies the electron-ion recombination, thus $PY = PY(E_0, \vec{E}_{\text{drift}}(x, y, z, t))$. This is the case because the recombination probability of an electron with an ionized Xe molecule (Xe_2^+) generates an excited Xe molecule (Xe_2^*) which emits a vacuum-ultraviolet (VUV) photon (see [section 2.2.2](#)). Different reasons cause a time dependency of \vec{E}_{drift} , such as the charge accumulation on PTFE surfaces and possible changes in the running conditions such as the voltages in the electrode configuration. The interaction position also impacts the probability that a produced photon hits one of the photomultiplier tubes (PMTs), as light is absorbed non uniformly in the detector. This effect is taken into account by the light collection

Figure 3.1: Relative light collection efficiency L_c as function of z (left) and ϕ (right) for different radial regions (colors). Plots taken from [84].

efficiency $\varepsilon_L = \varepsilon_L(x, y, z)$. Moreover, there is an additional efficiency loss due to the quantum efficiency ε_{QE} , which is the probability of a photon hitting a PMT to make one photoelectron (PE), and the charge collection efficiency ε_{CE} of PEs within the PMT. The final LY reads [84]:

$$LY = \frac{S1(\vec{E}_{\text{drift}}(x, y, z, t), E_0, x, y, z)}{E_0} = \varepsilon_L(x, y, z) \cdot PY(E_0, \vec{E}_{\text{drift}}(x, y, z, t)) \cdot \varepsilon_{QE} \cdot \varepsilon_{CE}. \quad (3.1)$$

A cylindrical coordinate system (R, ϕ, z) , where $z = 0$ is the plane of the gate mesh, is usually used in XENONnT. To obtain the three-dimensional correction map for the spatial dependence of the S1 signal, homogeneously distributed calibration sources are used, such as $^{83\text{m}}\text{Kr}$ that emits two gamma lines of 32.1 keV and 9.4 keV.

Evaluating the mean of the S1 distribution in discrete (R, ϕ) -regions and in slices of z and normalizing to its average across the TPC $\langle S1 \rangle$, the relative light collection efficiency $L_c = \varepsilon_L(x, y, z) \cdot PY(E_0, \vec{E}_{\text{drift}}(x, y, z, t))$ is obtained as shown in figure 3.1.

Introducing p_{dpe} the probability of the PMT photocathode to emit two PE when absorbing one photon, the corrected **cS1** used for energy reconstruction can be obtained as [86]:

$$g'_1(x, y, z) = (1 + p_{\text{dpe}}) \cdot \varepsilon_L(x, y, z) \cdot \varepsilon_{QE} \cdot \varepsilon_{CE}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$cS1 = S1 \frac{g_1}{g'_1(x, y, z)}, \quad (3.3)$$

where g_1 is the average of $g'_1(x, y, z)$ over the active detector volume.

Correction to S2 Signal

The presence in the LXe of electronegative impurities such as O_2 , H_2O , CO_2 results in an exponential loss in the number of ionization electrons which depends on the

electron lifetime τ_e and the z position of the event (see section 2.2.3). This is the most relevant spatial correction to the S2 signal. Introducing the gas gain $G(x,y)$, which is the number of PE for each electron extracted into the GXe volume and ϵ_{ext} the extraction efficiency for the drifted electrons, the corrected **cS2** used for energy reconstruction can be obtained as:

$$g'_2(x, y) = \epsilon_{\text{ext}} \cdot G(x, y), \quad (3.4)$$

$$\text{cS2} = \text{S2} \frac{g_2}{g'_2(x, y)} e^{z/(\tau_e \cdot v_d)}, \quad (3.5)$$

where g_2 is the average of $g'_2(x, y)$ over the active volume. As the purification procedure is continuous, τ_e changes over time. For this reason, it is estimated on a daily basis from mono-energetic α decays of from ^{222}Rn decay chain. Moreover, it is evaluated more accurately every couple of weeks with $^{83\text{m}}\text{Kr}$, measuring its two consecutive decays as a function of the electron drift time.

LXe Fiducialization

The reconstructed position of the events is used to segment the detector volume. The signal from WIMP particles is assumed to be distributed uniformly throughout the LXe volume. In contrast, many categories of background events are more concentrated near the walls of the detector (see section 2.4). Exploiting the self-shielding properties of the LXe, the signal over background ratio is increased, resulting in higher sensitivity for rare events. The final fiducial volume is currently an object of study for the XENONnT experiment. It could have different shapes, such as cylindrical or ellipsoid, including about 4 t of LXe out of a total of 5.9 t. The shape selection will be driven by the optimization of the spatial distribution of the background from detector materials and external sources.

3.1.2 PMT Arrays

The TPC is instrumented with 494 R11410-21 Hamamatsu 3" (7.62 cm) PMTs [97], assembled in two arrays at the top and the bottom, to detect both primary (S1) and secondary Xe scintillation light (S2).

$$\left\| \begin{array}{l} \# \text{ PMTs Top Array} \\ \# \text{ PMTs Bottom Array} \end{array} \right| \begin{array}{l} 253 \\ 241 \end{array} \left\|$$

The PMTs of both arrays follow an **hexagonal packing arrangement** to obtain a high filling factor. This allows the whole structure to be more resilient to non-functional PMTs due to a higher PMT density and to maximize the LCE. Some PMTs in the top and bottom array are switched off and excluded by the data analysis due to malfunctions such as vacuum leaks, low single photoelectron (SPE) acceptance or impulsive light emission (flashing). The number of dead PMTs usually grows throughout the life of the experiment as new problems arise.

Figure 3.2: Example of S2 patterns of an event detected during the commissioning of XENONnT and tagged as α -decay of the ^{214}Po atomic nucleus. In this process the α particle has a kinetic energy of $E_\alpha \simeq 7.68$ MeV [99]. The hue of the color indicates the signal size in photoelectrons. From the patterns the PMTs switched off due to their malfunctioning can be noticed.

3.2 Conventional Method for Position Reconstruction in XENONnT

In dual-phase TPC experiments, usually, the position in the plane (x, y) and along z (the direction of \vec{E}_{drift}) are reconstructed with two different approaches.

3.2.1 X-Y Position

The position in the (x, y) plane is obtained from the hit pattern on the top PMT array of the delayed S2 signal. The electrons entering the gaseous phase next to the top array create photons within (in average) the first 2.7 mm. The generated photons then go through at least other $\simeq 6.9$ cm of GXe before arriving at PMT's windows. The spot on the pattern is highly localized, as can be seen in figure 3.2. The size of the signal detected by each PMT is called area per channel and it is given in the number of photoelectrons emitted by the photocathode. The name area refers to the integration of the pulse distribution from which the number of photoelectrons is obtained [98].

Several (x, y) S2-based position reconstruction algorithms have been developed and tested for XENONnT. They can be divided into two categories, in the first one there are three deep learning algorithms: multilayer perceptron (MLP), convolutional neural network (CNN), and graph convolutional network (GCN). A simulation-driven approach is used in all those three cases: the models are trained on simulated data. Different datasets were created, generating events uniformly in a plane at a fixed depth. Concretely, a variable or fixed number of electrons, depending on the dataset (e.g. randomly in the range $[1, 2000]$), is injected just below the gate.

The second category is made up of physics-based methods. At the current stage, there is only one algorithm implemented: a maximum unbinned log-likelihood (LLH) fitter. The likelihood, which encodes the degree of difference between the observed and expected distribution of photons, is minimized using the Minuit2 C++ library [100]. This approach is based on the knowledge of the physical processes and the detector response. In theory, it is better than algorithms based on machine learning (ML), in

particular, due to the over-parameterized black-box nature of the latter, which often makes tricky to understand the predicted results. In practice, already from XENON1T, it has not been possible to model likelihood so well to exceed the accuracy of ML-based models and, above all, the time required to infer the position of an event with LLH is significantly longer, as it is shown in table 3.1.

Model	Resolution ¹ $\sigma_{x,y}$ [cm]	Parameters	Execution Time ² [us/event]
MLP	0.368	58k	34.3
CNN	0.364	52k	94.2
GCN	0.386	23k	30.6
LLH	0.424	×	4.4×10^4

Table 3.1: Some performance metrics of S2-based position reconstruction algorithms in the XENONnT experiment. The results refer to the application of the models on a test set coming from simulations generated with waveform simulator (WFSim)[101]. Validation on data from the commissioning phase of the XENONnT experiment does not show any significant degradation of performance for any of the models, as long as a signal with similar S2 area is considered.

Some substantial and conceptual differences in the three deep learning models listed in table 3.1 are quickly described in the following. In most of the computer vision tasks, CNN models perform better w.r.t. MLPs, thanks to three principles known as sparse interactions, weight-sharing, and equivariant representations, which are encoded in the convolutional layers [103]. As an object in an image, the peak on the PMT array can be found in any position of the pattern, but it maintains some common features. In addition, to identify those features, is not necessary to look at the whole image simultaneously. Concretely, as in MLPs the output of each PMT is just placed in a 1-D vector, the spatial structure of the problem is not taken into account. On the other hand, this is exploited and preserved by CNN models. The convolution kernels slide along the input providing an output equivariant to translation, also known as feature map. As the layers are not fully connected, this aspect should make the model more robust to overfitting and, in particular, to noises such as the presence in the hit pattern of a single electron S2 that is far away from the main S2. Moreover, thanks to parameter sharing, the learning of the parameters is extremely efficient in memory requirements and statistical efficiency (examples needed for the training) w.r.t a fully connected network.

The main difference between CNNs and GNNs is that the first needs to work with Euclidean structured data, while the latter is the generalized version of CNN that can operate on non-Euclidean structured data. The structure is defined by a graph where each link connecting two input nodes is encoded in the so-called adjacency matrix. As PMTs both in the bottom and top array form a hexagon on a hexagonal lattice, the GCN models use a "hexagonal" graph generated by connecting the PMTs next to each other. As done by CNNs, GCNs learn the features by inspecting neighbouring nodes.

¹The results refer to a test set not included in the training of the model with an amplitude of a signal of 200 injected S2 electrons, see text for more information.

²Runtime performances refer to the CPU cores on Midway2 [102] computing cluster of the University of Chicago made available for each XENONnT data analyst.

Figure 3.3: Impact of drift field distortion on position reconstruction. (Left) Reconstructed (x, y) position of the uniformly distributed $^{83\text{m}}\text{Kr}$ population before correcting for the electric field distortion. Black segments are the 24 PTFE reflector panels that are not in contact with the ring-shaped electrodes surrounding the TPC, while magenta are the panels that are in contact. (Right) Reconstructed (r, z) position of events close to the TPC edge in three different time periods before and after the correction. Horizontal error bars are the radial width of the event distribution, while vertical error bars mark the z bin width. The TPC wall is drawn as a vertical black dashed line. Plots taken from [84].

3.2.2 Z Position

The z position of an event is obtained from the drift velocity v_d of the electrons along the TPC and their drift time t_d . The latter is obtained from the difference between the S1 average time and the S2 average time. Evaluating the maximum drift time and knowing the length of the TPC, one can determine the drift velocity v_d . As the liquid level extends above the gate, it is necessary to subtract the average time that an electron needs to drift from the gate to the liquid level. In XENON1T the z -resolution reached values down to 0.5 mm [85].

3.2.3 Correction for Electric Field Distortion

Electron attachment on PTFE reflectors and electric field leakage through the cathode electrode are two of the reasons that cause the non-uniformity of the drift field [104]. All the available algorithms show an inward bias in reconstructing the radius for events close to the TPC wall, caused by the inward bias of the field lines at the TPC edge. This effect was also observed in XENON1T, and it is visible as the reconstructed positions from the homogeneously distributed $^{83\text{m}}\text{Kr}$ calibration source reveals a “bite” structure, as shown in figure 3.3.

A three-dimensional correction in (r, z, φ) is applied to fix that problem. The map is obtained by binning the active volumes in φ sectors and z slices and interpolating them to ensure a uniform distribution of $^{83\text{m}}\text{Kr}$ calibration events. In parallel to the latter data driven method, an accurate 3D electrical field simulation to be used for this purpose is currently under investigation. Accumulation of electrons on PTFE panels grows with time becoming more and more important, for this reason, periodically, is necessary to re-calibrate the position corrections.

3.3 A Novel Approach: S1 3D Position Reconstruction

The following sections introduce a new method for (x,y,z) position reconstruction developed within this thesis in the XENONnT experiment using both top and bottom S1 PMT hit patterns. After having transformed the data from a hexagonal structure to a rectangular one with the so-called axial transformation [105], the reconstruction is obtained exploiting a CNN model.

3.3.1 Motivation

The development of position reconstruction methods based on the S2 hit pattern on the top array and drift time is definitely the choice that leads to the best resolution. Nevertheless, some situations require an alternative approach. Firstly, there are areas in the TPC which are sensitive to the S1 but not to the S2 signals. This is the case of the six cm-thick layers of LXe between the bottom PMT array and the cathode, in which ~ 250 kg of LXe is present. Moreover, \vec{E}_{drift} lines are bent inwards in the region close to the wall due to edge effects. To mitigate it and obtain a more uniform \vec{E}_{drift} , field-shaping rings (FSRs) are used. However, increasing their voltage to straighten the field lines of \vec{E}_{drift} they create charge insensitive regions, drifting electrons against PTFE reflector panels: it is necessary to find a good trade-off between these two effects. From the results of some simulation, the area in the bottom part of the TPC close to the wall could be insensitive to the S2 signal [106]. A non negligible amount of S1-S2 mismatches can be found, most of which are removed with physics-based data quality cuts. Nonetheless, there are remaining events, known as accidental coincidences, that are not removed. One way to exclude them could be to find a mismatch in the reconstructed positions by an S1-only method and the standard S2-based methods (see section 3.2).

3.3.2 CNN with Hexagonal Binning: Axial Transformation

PMTs in the bottom and top of the TPC are structured as a hexagon on a hexagonal lattice, formed by each PMT. The hexagonal packing arrangement is the highest-density lattice packing even if circles are used instead of the hexagon as elementary cell, as proved in 1773 by Joseph Louis Lagrange. The hexagonal arrangement of the PMTs in both the arrays maximize the LCE, the photocathode coverage and the uniformity of the detected signals. As the pixels of an image have an orthogonal grid topology, the different elements and operations used in CNN for image-related tasks are developed and implemented for rectangular data (for instance kernels, input scanning, pooling, etc.). For this reason, changing the coordinate systems, it is necessary to index the hexagonal grid, in order to store the data into a 2D memory array so that:

1. neighbourhood relations among pixels are preserved,
2. the necessary introduction of padding elements is minimized, as it causes substantial memory and computation overheads,
3. square convolution kernels can be exploited for hexagonal convolution.

The hexagonal lattice structure contains all possible points that can be obtained as an integer linear combination of two basis vectors e_1 and e_2 separated by an angle of 60 degrees. The selected axial coordinate system, given $u, v \in \mathbb{Z}$, represents the pixel

Figure 3.4: (Left) The first step of the axial transformation for a hit pattern from the top PMT array of an S1 signal generated with WFSim. The padding zeros (cyan circles) are added to the original shape to fill in the parallelogram. (Right) Obtained rectangular representation shifting the rows, so that they are aligned.

centered at $ue_1 + ve_2$ by the coordinates (u, v) . The ordinary convolution in the case of CNN, performed scanning the input with a rectangular kernel, relies on the additive structure of \mathbb{Z}^2 [107]. As both the square and hexagonal lattice are isomorphic to \mathbb{Z}^2 , this allows using rectangular kernels if the hexagonally shaped inputs are rectangular in the axial coordinates [105]. A visualization of the axial transformation can be seen in figure 3.4.

Before this work, in XENONnT a CNN model was used exclusively for the “standard” S2-based (x, y) position reconstruction (see section 3.2.1) and a double-width transformation [105] was adopted to tackle the hexagonally shaped inputs. The application of the new axial transformation allows to reduce the number of padding elements by about 40 % which results in a substantial reduction of the run time (by about 50 %) of the reconstruction of the position of one event when used inside Straxen (STReaming ANalysis for XENON EXPERIMENTs) [108], the analysis framework for XENONnT. The use of the new transformation brings no deterioration in performance in terms of bias and precision.

3.3.3 Input Data and Task Goal

To reconstruct the position from the S1 signal, both bottom and top arrays are required. The patterns strongly depend on the z position of the interaction, as can be seen in figure 3.5. In fact, the detected signal comes directly from the interaction point where, accordingly with the deposited energy, a certain number of photons are emitted uniformly. Before feeding the inputs into the network, the signal amplitudes in the PMTs are normalized, dividing each pixel for the maximum one of the two arrays. In this way, the relationship between the pattern in the top and bottom arrays is conserved, as this is related to the z -coordinate at which the event occurred. Usually, data preprocessing operations are used to stabilize and improve the convergence of the gradient descent optimization algorithms. For many deep learning modes, it is quite a common choice to rescale and standardize the features, however, this makes sense when they are (partially) independent, which is not the case for images, and this is even more true if you want to carry out a regression task. The network returns the coordinate of the interactions,

3.3. A Novel Approach: S1 3D Position Reconstruction

Figure 3.5: Hit patterns of three events generated with WFSim with a fixed amplitude. (Top/Bottom) Interaction happened in the upper/lower part of the TPC: the pattern is peaked in the top/bottom array. The task of placing the red cross on the peak is easier. (Center) The signal is spread all around the arrays. The photons have to travel a longer distance to reach one of the two arrays during which mainly the isotropic radial expansion, but also the Rayleigh scattering ($\lambda_{\text{Rayleigh}} \simeq 30 \text{ cm}$) widen their spatial distribution. The full internal reflections at the liquid–gas interface are the main reason that determines the higher detection of photons by the bottom array. The different path that they need to travel is of secondary importance: after the gate, the photons directed downwards have to cross $\simeq 6 \text{ cm}$ of LXe, while those directed upwards $\simeq 5 \text{ mm}$ of LXe and $\simeq 7.2 \text{ cm}$ of GXe.

3.3. A Novel Approach: S1 3D Position Reconstruction

Set version.number ³	S1 Photons [#]	Size [#]	LXe Absorption Length [m]	GXe Absorption Length [m]
0.0	200 k	500 k	50	0.3
0.1	500 k	500 k	50	0.3
0.2	50 k	500 k	50	0.3
0.3	30-750 k	1 M	50	0.3
1.0	30-750 k	150 k	10	100
1.1	30-750 k	150 k	17.5	100
1.2	30-750 k	150 k	31	100
1.3	30-750 k	150 k	50	100
1.4	30-750 k	150 k	55	100
1.5	30-750 k	150 k	100	100

Table 3.2: Description of the simulated datasets used in this work. The set version shown in the first column is changed after introducing a new optical map (see [section 3.4.3](#) for more info). In datasets 1.i, the number of data points is reduced, as it was realized that this does not have a significant impact on the training considering hypothesis classes with a model complexity such as those considered in [section 3.3.6](#).

concretely $(x, y) \in [0, 66.4]$ cm and $z \in [0, -148.6]$ cm, although, the output has not been constrained to be in this range.

3.3.4 MC Training Datasets - Simulation-Driven Approach

In particle physics, when supervised learning models are used, training sets are generated generally through Monte Carlo simulation. Compared to many traditional fields where deep learning is applied, in particle physics it is possible to obtain remarkably accurate generative models thanks to simulation tools for producing synthetic data from first principles, considering both the microphysics of particle interactions and the detector description. The careful composition of the data in the training set is one of the best ways to control the systematic effects by which the model can be affected. On the one hand, if a perfect match between the actual data and the simulation is achieved, it is possible to generate a training dataset with any distributions for the variables that we know to modify the simulated/real data more radically. On the other hand, if there is any systematic mismodeling between simulated and real data, applying the model to the latter will likely propagate, even increasing the systematic mismatch. In WFSim, after the generation of raw signal waveforms, they are fed to the same signal processor used on real data, Straxen, to use the same processing algorithms, among which the peak finder. In the end, the final patterns are obtained and stored.

3.3.5 Model Selection and Training

The deep learning model selected in this work is a CNN, for the reason explained in [section 3.2.1](#). Although this problem seems perfect for using the great expressive power of GNNs, which operate on graph domain, those models often struggle with time complexity [110]. The intention to obtain an algorithm with a good time efficiency is justified by its possible usage for “online” analysis such as the online monitoring or the fast analysis. The value of the peak rate in the XENONnT experiment after some preprocessing and clustering analysis depends on the running condition and the related presence of a calibration source. Generally it is of the order of few thousands of hertz.

³The change of the name w.r.t. the ones known in the XENON collaboration is done here only for the sake of clarity. The set 0.0 refers to the 1000001, the 1.0 to 1000021, according to [109].

Figure 3.6: Design selected for the CNN model. After the application of the axial transformation, the patterns are fed into the two independent branches whose outputs are flattened and concatenated in a feedforward model, which gives as output the three coordinates of the position of the interaction vertex.

It is necessary that the execution time of the model for a single event is compatible with the peak rate, taking into account the computing resources available for the XENON collaboration.

The PMT arrays still have a periodical structure as they are in a hexagonal packing arrangement. For this reason, compared to the most general possible case that an adjacency matrix can describe, it is a sub-case with remarkable regularity. Addressing the problem with a transformation, such as the axial one, is one of the simplest approaches, among those that take into account the structure of the data, which is not the case of the MLP. The second choice made is to process the two patterns related to the top and bottom arrays with two separate convolutional branches, as shown in figure 3.6. Although this results in a significant increase of the model complexity, the patterns observed on the two arrays are not identical, given the non-symmetry of the TPC, as described in figure 3.5. In this way the convolutional feature maps are concatenated and they are treated as independent for the remaining feedforward part of the architecture.

3.3.6 Hyperparameter Optimization

To implement a model selection with a hyperparameter optimization procedure and to estimate the generalization error of the chosen model, it is necessary to divide the initial dataset into 3 subsets: training, validation, and test sets (the first division can be circumvented by using k-fold cross-validation [111]). The machine learning community refers to hyperparameters of the model, the ones that the training procedure cannot tweak, but they must be fixed from the outside (see for instance table 3.3), the rest, e.g. node weights, are known as parameters. In our case, the search for a predictor has already been limited to models with the general structure shown in figure 3.6. Fixing n different combinations of the hyperparameters a set of n hypothesis classes is identified:

$$\mathcal{H} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \mathcal{H}_i, \quad (3.6)$$

where each H_i is an hypothesis class and \mathcal{H} the space explored by the model selection process. To perform model selection it is necessary to train different model classes on the training set so that a set of hypothesis is obtained, i.e. a set of predictors with both hyperparameters and parameters fixed:

$$K = \{h_1, \dots, h_n\} .$$

Then, the loss score on a validation set, not used for the training, is used to pick one hypothesis $h_* \in K$, concretely the predictor with the best performance on the validation set is selected. After that, the hypothesis class that contains h_* is retrained on the union of the training and validation set. In conclusion, it is necessary to estimate the generalization error of the final hypothesis, computing the loss function, i.e. the performance measure of the model optimized during the training, on the test set, which is not used until now and is not involved in the selection of the final hypothesis.

Manual hyperparameter tuning to select different hypothesis classes to train is often relatively inefficient and does not allow to explore a large number of combinations. In principle, each of them could lead to better results unless there is some experience on the particular task, which can act as prior knowledge. The most common practice to automatically select hyperparameters is called grid search. In that case, for each hyperparameter, a small finite set of values are selected. Then, the tuples of hyperparameters to define the hypothesis classes are found with the Cartesian product of the different sets. The most severe problem with this approach is the number of training and evaluation trials required, which for m hyperparameters, each taking at most n values grows as $\mathcal{O}(n^m)$. To encode some prior knowledge and explore a broader range smoothly for each hyperparameter, the random search approach is used in this work. Random search has been shown to converge much faster to good values of the hyperparameters, particularly when only a small number of them heavily influence the final performance [112]. In table 3.3 the values of the hyperparameters used for random search are reported. As the two branches of the model have been constrained to be symmetric, the number of layer in row 1 of table 3.3 refers to both. The extraction from the given array follows a multinoulli distribution with the probabilities given in row 2, e.g. $n=2$ is extracted with $p=0.25$. The number of kernels of each convolutional layer is extracted from a Gaussian distribution with mean reported in row 3 and with standard deviation $\sigma = \mu/(2 + i)$, where i is the position of the considered convolutional layer in the branch, e.g. for the first layer $i=0$, for the second $i=1$, etc. The deeper is the position of the layer in the network, the less spread is the distribution. The continuous output of the Gaussian is then rounded.

The size of the kernels of each layer is set by extracting from the multinoulli defined by the vector in row 4 and the probabilities of row 5, where each row i of the matrix refers to the extraction probabilities of the layer of position i . E.g. in the first layer, the kernels will have size 3 or 5 with probability 10% each. In the rows 6-7 uniform distribution on a log-scale is used, where the symbols $\mathcal{U}_{\mathbb{R}}/\mathcal{U}_{\mathbb{N}}$ refer to continuous/discrete uniform distribution over real/natural. In rows 9 and 11 objects are called from the packages `torch.optim` [113] and `torch.nn` [114] respectively, where the source code is present and references are documented in detail.

If there is not any heuristic, the prior distributions are selected according to the principle of maximum ignorance. Many of the values and distribution present in the table 3.3 are chosen learning from some trials made manually. All the networks presented in this section are implemented using the open source machine learning library PyTorch

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ROW	HYPERPARAMETER	VALUES/ELEMENTS	SELECTED
1	Number Conv Layers	[3,4,5]	4
2	Prob Number Conv Layers	[0.25, 0.65, 0.10]	
3	μ Kernels	[16, 24, 32, 64]	[18, 25, 37, 63]
4	Dimension Kernels	[3, 5, 7, 9]	[7, 5, 3, 3]
5	Prob Dimension Kernels	[[0.10, 0.10, 0.40, 0.40],[0.40, 0.50, 0.10, 0], [0.70,0.30, 0, 0], [0.70, 0.30, 0, 0]]	
6	Number Fully-Connected Layers	[1,2]	2
7	Learning Rate	$\log_lr \sim \mathcal{U}_{\mathbb{R}}(-3.5, -1.5) \rightarrow lr = 10^{\log_lr}$	-2.92
8	L ₂ Penalty	$\log_l2 \sim \mathcal{U}_{\mathbb{R}}(-4, -2.5) \rightarrow l2 = 10^{\log_l2}$	-3.87
9	Optimizer	[optim.Adam, optim.Adamax, optim.AdamW]	optim.Adam
10	Epochs	$\mathcal{U}_{\mathbb{N}}(150 \div 300)$	198
11	Activation Function	[nn.ELU, nn.Hardswish, nn.ReLU, nn.Mish, nn.LeakyReLU, nn.SELU]	nn.ELU
12	Dropout Probability	$\mathcal{U}_{\mathbb{R}}(0, 0.2)$	0.0
13	Type Pooling	[average, max]	average

Table 3.3: Values of the hyperparameters used for the random search, in the last column those selected by the process are shown. For further details see the text.

[115, 116]. As a regression problem is considered, the mean squared error (MSE) loss function is chosen. The mean absolute error is also tried, which in theory should penalize more small errors than MSE, helping the model to achieve better precision, however, the benefit is not verified in this particular case. In the random search procedure the k-fold cross-validation is not included, reducing a lot the computational time. In fact, after some trials, it is noticed that the difference of the validation loss on different folds is not significant and there is enough data to do the training properly, even splitting the starting dataset in three subsets (80-10-10)%. Before starting, the training weights and biases of each layer are initialized following Kaiming initialization or a.k.a. He initialization [117], which is particularly recommended for models using ReLU activation function or its variations/ successors, to avoid slow convergence. Moreover, it helps with vanishing and exploding gradient issues, particularly at the start of the learning process. The training is carried out using a minibatch gradient descent optimization algorithm, concretely the adaptive learning rate Adam optimizer or some of its variation that can be found in table 3.3. In the minibatch gradient descent algorithms the gradient of the loss function is not evaluated using all points of the training set, but with a small set of `batch_size` dimension extracted randomly. After every evaluation of the gradient, the model's internal parameters are updated. In this context the number of epochs denotes the number of complete passes through the entire training dataset. After few attempts the batch size is kept constant at the not high value of 64, bearing in mind the practical recommendations given in [118]. This may seem counterintuitive as the fewer points used for the evaluation the less accurate it is. However, by computing the actual gradient direction (averaging over the whole training set) one gets the steepest descent direction, but just locally, which may not be the one to follow in a broader vision. For this reason getting a more accurate estimate could be wasteful. On the other hand, increasing the frequency of the updates helps to explore the parameter space more and faster. Thanks to the statistical fluctuations injected in the gradient estimation, a form of

Figure 3.7: (Left) Selected model architecture after the random search. (Right) Learning curve of the selected model.

regularization is introduced. After some attempts, even if the network architecture is not deep, it was found that the adaptive reparametrization known as batch normalization [119] performed on post-activation values seems to increase slightly the precision of the models and for this reason is included after each convolutional layer. Different works have underlined the regularizing effect of batch normalization, making unnecessary the use dropout to mitigate overfitting [120]. After noting that the model did not show overfitting and the performances on the validation set were a little worse, dropout was excluded from the training.

The fraction of the S1 signal observed by the top array, “S1 area fraction top” or simply S1 AFT, is deeply related to the z position of the event. Thereby, it was tried to concatenate the S1 AFT quantity directly to the flatten layer of the model to improve the prediction of the z position. Since no significant improvements are found, it is reasonable to assume that one of the hidden variables extracted by the model is closely related to S1 AFT.

To explore many models in the random search procedure an early stopping condition is implemented. When too many epochs pass without the model’s performance on the validation set improves, the training process is interrupted. In the first 40% of the epochs the training cannot be stopped. After that, for each epoch if in the last 20% of the total number of epochs an improvement of 3% compared to the previous 20% has not occurred, then the training is stopped. In total, more than 200 hypothesis classes defined by extractions following the [table 3.3](#) are tried.

3.3.7 The Selected Model

In the last years, architectures specialised in image-related tasks such as SENet [121], Inception-v4 [122], VGG16 [123], achieved excellent results, for example, on the ImageNet project [124]. The model currently chosen in this work is much simpler and has orders of magnitude of parameters less. It is crucial to remember that one of the main reasons to use a deep learning technique for position reconstruction in XENONnT is the significant runtime reduction compared to a physical based model. In the Straxen analysis framework, position reconstruction is a relatively small part of the data processing chain needed to fully reconstruct an event. The resources that each XENON analyzer is provided to carry out physics analyses come from the Midway2 [102] computing cluster of the University of Chicago and are much more limited than those used by the projects mentioned above. Most importantly, at the moment, once the model is trained and loaded on Straxen, predictions are made using CPUs, which severely limits runtime of orders of magnitude. There are some GPU nodes available in the Midway2 cluster, however, they are quite old and the overhead in the stream of the analysis due to jobs management to use them is significant. These are some reasons why it is essential to reduce model complexity as much as possible. The introduction of residual or inception modules into the network structure has not resulted in decisive improvements to justify the increase in runtime. The GPU resources situation seems to be improving with the forthcoming introduction of Midway3 [125]. This will require to consider more carefully what improvements can come from deeper architectures. The model selection is performed on the dataset number 0.3 according to table 3.2. The selected model and the related learning curve can be seen in figure 3.7, from the last it is evident that the model shows a good fit. The execution time on the resources available on the Midway2 cluster is $\simeq 320 \mu\text{s}$ per event.

3.4 Simulation-Driven Models

In this section, the performances of several predictors obtained training the best-found hypothesis class according to section 3.3.7 on the various simulated datasets listed in

Figure 3.8: Performances of the model trained and tested on different simulated datasets listed in table 3.2 for different radii of the simulated events. The subscript R refers to the reconstructed quantity, while the subscript T refers to the Monte Carlo truth. The solid line refers to the median, while the dotted lines are 1-sigma uncertainty

Figure 3.9: Performances of the predictor trained and tested on different simulated datasets for different z position of the simulated events.

the table 3.2 are shown.

3.4.1 Proof of Concept Testing on Simulations

Since a S1-based position reconstruction method for a dual-phase TPC is not currently available, first of all it is important to check the validity of the technique exclusively on Monte Carlo simulations. The performances of the model trained and tested on several simulated datasets, that differ from each other for the amplitude of the signal, are studied below. In the present work, if not otherwise stated, the performances of the reconstruction of the y position are not shown because they are analogous to the one of the x position. Both in figures 3.8 and 3.9 it is evident that if the signal amplitude is larger then the performance is better. Moreover, the reconstruction of the planar variables (x , y) undergoes a degradation near the wall and in the centre of the TPC.

Figure 3.10: 3D position reconstruction resolution as a function of the number of emitted photons of the event for different predictors coming from the same hypothesis class, but trained on different datasets. Each model is tested on the same simulated data coming from the dataset 0.3.

Figure 3.11: ^{228}Th decay chain with the calibration source ^{220}Rn highlighted in azure. For the α decays of the daughter nuclei holds $E_\alpha \gtrsim 6$ MeV, they are energetic events for a low-energy experiment such as XENONnT.

The first behaviour is due to edge effects such as the truncation of the pattern in that region, the latter is caused by the pattern spread (see figure 3.5).

To studies the generalization capabilities of the model on different amplitudes the 3D position reconstruction resolution for different training set is shown in figure 3.10. It can be clearly seen that to achieve the best performance over a wide range of energies, it is necessary to train the model over a broad domain of amplitudes (red curve). This justifies why in sets 1.i in table 3.2 only samples with a number of emitted photons between [30-750] k were generated.

3.4.2 Testing the First Optical Map: α Decays in ^{220}Rn Data

The selected model trained on the dataset number 0.3 is the first to be tested. The performances are evaluated both on a test set from the same simulated dataset used to obtain the training set and on actual data from the commissioning phase of XENONnT. The noble gas isotope ^{220}Rn ($T_{1/2} \simeq 55.6$ s) is one of the sources used in the periodic calibration runs in ultra-low background experiments. Specifically, a source of electrodeposited ^{228}Th emits ^{220}Rn (see figure 3.11), which through the purification

CUT	MOTIVATION
($40\text{k} < \text{S1 area} < 200\text{k}$) [PE] ($40 < \text{S1 width } 50\text{p area} < 300$) [ns] $\text{S2 area} > 500$ [PE]	α Decays are energetic $E_\alpha \gtrsim 6$ MeV.
$\text{S2 AFT} > 0.7$	Crude selection physical S2 signal.
(S2, S1) space	Mainly rejection of γ background.
(S1 AFT, drift time) space	Events without a dependence between S1 AFT and drift time are unphysical.
(S2 width, drift time) space	Events without an increase of S2 width with drift time, due to diffusion, are unphysical.

Table 3.4: In the first row, S1 area refers to the size of the S1 signal computed adding up the output of each PMT's channel of both top and bottom array. S1 width 50p area is the width of the S1 signal which contains 50% of the peak area. S1/S2 AFT refers to the fraction of the S1/S2 signal detected by the top array. The S2 width refers to the S2 pulse width at 50 % height (FWHM). The last three listened cuts are represented in figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Representation of the last three cuts listened and motivated in table 3.4 .

system is mixed into the detector volume and decays completely within a few days [126]. The chosen data are the energetic α decays present in the spectrum of ^{220}Rn , shown in figure 3.11.

Energetic events are chosen to test the models as the resolution of the algorithms is expected to improve significantly with the energy of the event (see figure 3.10). To select α decays some data quality cuts are applied, which are summarized in table 3.4.

To test the model, 10^5 events respecting the cuts presented in the first two rows of table 3.4 and coming from ^{220}Rn calibration runs are considered. After the application of the remaining cuts, 23514 events are left.

In the simulated test set, having the Monte Carlo truth, the position of the interaction vertex is known, while in the data, this information is not available in principle. In this second case, the true value of the event is assumed to be the reconstructed by the S2-based MLP and corrected with the field distortion maps (see section 3.2.3). As can be seen by comparing S2 (see figure 3.2) and S1 (see figure 3.5) patterns, it is implausible that a method based on the latter would have comparable performance with the former, since S1 patterns are highly more spread, in particular in the centre of the TPC. Considering the z position, the standard value is used as the true value (see section 3.2.2).

As shown in figure 3.13 good performances (blue lines) are achieved when the model is used with simulated data. The application on data, firstly, leads to a general worsening of about $\times 2$ in the resolution of (x, y) . Nonetheless, important biases are not introduced with respect to the resolution in those directions. The same behaviour also occurs for plots such as $\Delta x/\Delta y$ vs. R_T or Δx vs. z_T (not shown here for brevity). Secondly and most importantly, an enormous bias in z position is found when the model is applied to

Figure 3.13: Distribution of the difference between the reconstructed coordinate obtained with the S1-based CNN and the “true” values for the x (left) and z (right) position (see text for more info).

the data, with a general upward push of the reconstructed position in the TPC. The bias is almost constant for different radii, while strong variations for different depths in Δz vs z_T are found (see orange curve figure 3.14).

The study of different simulations reveals the impact of mismatches between the simulations and the data on the performances, as discussed in section 3.4.3. The strategy of using deep learning to benchmark how well the simulations agree with the data was already followed in particular at LHC experiments [127]. For this reason, some attempts are made to improve the simulations, and the results are presented in the following section.

3.4.3 Testing the Second Optical Map: α Decays in ^{220}Rn Data

In the light of the bias presented in the last section on ^{220}Rn calibration data (see figure 3.13), new simulated training datasets were created, denoted as 1.x in table 3.2. A new optical map is used there, where the most notable change is the modification of the gas absorption length (30 cm \rightarrow 100 m). The previous value, originated from XENON1T, was used as an effective parameter to achieve a match between simulation and data and to correct missing details of S2 signal modelling. In addition, a parameter of the simulations which impacts most the change of the number of photons arriving at the two PMT’s arrays is the absorption length in LXe. Since the value of 50 m [70] is a reasonable assumption, but not a measured quantity in XENONnT, training sets with different values are tested to tune it better. Moreover, absorption length in LXe also depends on the cleanliness and the amount of impurities, so it can vary during the months of the detector operations. The results presented in figure 3.14 are an example showing how the predictions can provide hints about possible systematic mismatches between the simulations and the actual data. Referring to figure 3.14, the reconstruction of (x,y) is not affected largely by the change of the optical map and the variation of LXe absorption length (see top left plot). The slight degradation of the resolution compared to the model trained on 0.3 is probably due to the consistent reduction in the size of the training sets. In addition, fixed the new optical map, the change of the dataset does not seem to substantially modify the shape of the distributions for the reconstruction of the z position. The replacement of the optical map drastically modifies the bias in the

Figure 3.14: Performances of the model trained on different datasets generated with the new optical map for different LXe absorption lengths on ^{220}Rn calibration data from the commissioning phase of XENONnT.

reconstruction of z (see bottom centre plot). For a fixed depth, larger gas absorption lengths mean an increase in S1 AFT, which is most likely a variable used by the model to infer the z depth (see the end of section 3.3.7). In the training set generated with the initial optical map, for a given depth of the events, S1 AFT was underestimated. Applying it to the data results in an upward bias of the z position reconstruction (see orange curve bottom centre plot). The results seem to suggest that the optical model has to be improved to avoid such biases in the z reconstruction that are still present also using the updated optical map.

3.4.4 The Selected Simulation-Driven Model

The profound change caused by the optical map and the slight for different LXe absorption lengths suggests that the latter is not the central issue of the current MC-data mismatch. A reasonable and conservative value, LXe absorption lengths = 50 m, is considered for the final model selected from the simulation-driven approach. Some performance results of this model have already been shown in figure 3.14 and others are presented in the following.

A clear degradation of resolution is shown in figure 3.15 in the case of ^{220}Rn calibration data, but biases for different radii are tolerable if they are compared to respective resolutions. In addition, an important decrease of precision in the centre of the TPC for $\Delta x/\Delta y$ can be seen in figure 3.16, utterly in the case of data, but also present in the simulations. The latter effect can be explained with the pattern spread

Figure 3.15: Performances of the predictor trained on the dataset 1.3 for different radii both on a test set from the same simulated dataset used to obtain the training set and on ^{220}Rn calibration data from the commissioning phase of XENONnT.

Figure 3.16: Performances of the reconstruction as a function of z position of the events.

(see figure 3.5). Although the wavy pattern in Δz vs z in the case of data is far from acceptable, significant improvements have been achieved compared to the old optical map (see figure 3.14).

At the current stage, it is necessary to find a way to overcome the MC-data mismatch, particularly for the bias in the reconstruction of the z position. In fact, to obtain further improvements with this approach is unavoidable to rely on the simulation matching campaign that has not yet completed. There is a constant improvement by the XENON collaboration in that direction, however, it is unfeasible to solve the issue within the time of this thesis.

3.5 Data-Driven Model

To overcome the MC-data mismatch, a different approach is implemented. To be trained, supervised learning models require a dataset with the output variables, concretely the knowledge of the interaction position is needed for each event. This can be obtained considering the output of the default position reconstruction methods (see section 3.2), aware that a model based on the S1 signal cannot be more precise (see figure 3.5).

Figure 3.17: Event presenting a mismatch in the pairing of the S1 and S2 signal. The reconstruction of the event is completely distorted by the wrong pairing: it is necessary to cut out those events of the training/test sets.

3.5.1 Approach and Global Performances

The data-driven approach developed is based on a dataset of α decays from the ^{220}Rn decay chain in calibration data. Additional selection has to be performed to avoid wrongly matched S1 and S2 signals. In those events, in fact, a completely wrong reconstruction of the z position and a displacement between the patterns coming from the two signals is present (see figure 3.17).

They are drastically reduced by the application of data quality cuts (see table 3.4), but not completely removed. For this reason, for the training set, only those events for which the distance in (x,y) between the reconstruction of the selected simulation-driven model (see section 3.4.4) and the positions obtained with standard methods after the correction for the field distortion (see section 3.2.3) is less than 5 cm are considered. The cut is very stringent, however, sufficient statistics are available to apply it. In fact, it is preferred to make type-I errors, instead of accepting a false positive for the training set, which at the end consists in 257528 events ($\approx 52\%$ of the total). To test the model a dataset was created relaxing the cut to 12 cm, to not overestimate the performance,

Figure 3.18: Performances of the data-driven CNN model on the test set. Considerable improvement in the precision, particularly in the shape of the z position distribution w.r.t. the simulation-driven model.

but at the same time avoiding the inclusion of too many mismatches. The cut is passed by $\simeq 83\%$ of the events of the original dataset.

3.5.2 Performances for Different Zones of the Detector

Testing the performance of the data-driven model in different areas of the detector is fundamental to know eventual non-uniformity or systematic effects. For a more accurate list of plots see [appendix A](#), where the dependence of performances for different radii and depths has been decoupled by dividing the detectors into slices.

The inward pushing of the reconstructed position close to the edge is visible in the plot ΔR vs R^2 in [figure 3.19](#). This effect is also present in all the S2-based position reconstruction methods [128, 129] and it is due to the truncation of the pattern close to the wall. If the model were trained only on edge data, there would be likely no bias. On the other hand, being trained on complete and truncated patterns, it does not manage to return an unbiased prediction on both. Two strategies can be explored in the future to try to mitigate this issue, on the one hand an increase in the model complexity, on the other hand a weighting of the training dataset, with more data concentrated near the wall. The expected deterioration of performance in the center of TPC is less evident than before. This could suggest that in that area, where regression is more complicated, a slight general mismodelling of the simulated patterns can significantly deteriorate the precision of the simulation-driven model. In addition, although some oscillations are still present in the bias of ΔZ vs Z (see [figure 3.20](#)), probably due to the variation of the light collection efficiency (LCE) along the detector [70], there is a significant

Figure 3.19: Performances on the test set for different radii of the event.

Figure 3.20: Performances on the test set for different depths of the event.

improvement over the simulation-driven model.

3.5.3 Performances for Different Energies

Supervised learning algorithms struggle with generalizing, i.e. returning accurate predictions outside the domain they have been trained on. Considering an event occurred in a specific position, the S1 area per channel associated with each PMT changes if the deposited energy varies. The data-driven model was trained on a limited range of energy and with non-uniform distribution. It is impossible to obtain a uniform distribution, with this approach, over the whole spectrum of energies that XENONnT can probe. Concretely, the distribution of events is peaked on the energies of the α lines from ^{220}Rn decay chain in calibration data. Apart from the lack of Monte Carlo truth, this is another major limitation of using a data-driven approach. Position regression in a region of phase space less explored by the model seems not to introduce any critical bias, but only a degradation of the precision, as seen in figure 3.21.

An improvement of the resolution is expected in the case of a uniform distribution of the training set for larger values of the S1 area. This explains the improvement at high S1 area values shown in figure 3.21 even if the amount of training data decreases. The training set has not been made uniform, as the model performs better where more data are expected in ^{220}Rn calibration runs. The deterioration with less data in the training set only corresponds to a degradation of the resolution and not to the introduction of biased behavior, as can be seen in the plot ΔZ vs S1 area.

Figure 3.21: (Left) 3D position resolution as a function of the S1 area on the test set compared to the S1 area distribution of the training set.

(Right) Performance of z position reconstruction for different S1 areas.

3.5.4 Systematic Effects

One of the main aspects of the model to be achieved and controlled is its robustness. Many systematic effects may be present in the data and they may also vary at different times in the life of the experiment. Two effects are considered in the following : gain uncertainties and exclusion of some PMTs from the analysis.

Figure 3.22: Effect on the reconstruction performances of the perturbation with a pixel value depended gaussian noise.

Gain Stability

The signal detected by each PMT of the two arrays undergoes fluctuations mainly caused by PMT's gain instabilities. They are monitored periodically with a pulsed LED, configured to produce signals of a few photoelectrons, as described in [130]. In XENONnT gains are measured to be stable up to 2% with fluctuations dominated by statistical uncertainty [131], a similar result was obtained in XENON1T [132]. To simulate the impact on the detected signal by each PMT, all the pixels are perturbed with Gaussian noise of width, σ_{NOISE} , equals to a certain percentage of the value returned in each event by the considered sensor.

From figure 3.22 it is evident that the z position reconstruction is more sensitive to variations, as the regression task is more complicated. In bottom centre can be noticed that for large perturbations with, $\sigma_{\text{NOISE}} > 10\%$, the depth is downward biased reconstructed. This may be explained by the fact that a higher percentage of the signal is detected by the bottom array (see figure 3.5). Furthermore, the increase of the brightest PMTs outputs biases more the reconstruction of the z position w.r.t. its reduction. In general terms, the model exhibits noise robustness properties. In fact, considering a conservative value of a signal variation of 5%, the worsening of the precision is within 7 % for the (x, y) position and within 4 % for the z position without the introduction of any significant bias.

Figure 3.23: Reconstruction performances for a different number of switched off PMTs. Once again, it can be seen that the largest effect is on the z position reconstruction.

Missing PMTs

Although a rigorous calibration campaign is carried out for each PMT [97], conditions such as the operations at cryogenic conditions in LXe can cause operational issues (see section 3.1.2), which result in the exclusion of certain sensors. At the current stage, the data-driven version of the model presented in this work has been trained with events, where already 9 PMTs in normal running conditions are not taking data, concretely the channels {156, 164, 177, 352, 354, 362, 386, 393, 427} according to the indexing shown in figure 3.5. Usually, all deep learning algorithms used in XENONnT are retrained after switching off a PMT to minimize the impact on resolutions and biases. Nevertheless, it is essential to check the robustness of the performances in case they have to operate on events with additional missing channels. To carry out the study, an equal number of PMTs from the top and bottom arrays are randomly switched off in the test set. To obtain a statistically uniform effect, 10 different random draws for each total number of switched-off PMTs are merged. The results shown in figure 3.23 prove that zeroing randomly 2 PMTs for each array, the worsening of the precision is within 14 % for the (x, y) position and within 15 % for the z position without the introduction of any significant bias. The robustness shown by the model is sufficient, bearing in mind that the general strategy to follow is the retraining of the model according to the new configuration.

3.6 Performances on BiPo Coincidence

The performance of position reconstruction algorithms can be tested in a data-driven way with a coincidence, i.e. two events known to happen almost at the same position.

Figure 3.24: Decay chain of the radioactive noble gas ^{222}Rn , as part of the primordial ^{238}U chain. ^{238}U is the most common isotope of uranium and one of the main sources of natural terrestrial radioactivity.

The validation of the accuracy, however, is not guaranteed by this method, as the two reconstructed positions could be affected by the same bias. A possible coincidence in the XENONnT experiment is the one of the β decay of the ^{214}Bi nucleus ($E_{\text{max},\beta} \simeq 3.27 \text{ MeV}$) and the α decay of the ^{214}Po ($E_{\alpha} \simeq 7.83 \text{ MeV}$) [133]:

Those processes are present in the ^{222}Rn decay chain (see figure 3.24). The ^{222}Rn isotope, due to emanation from detector components, is uniformly distributed in the xenon itself and it forms the largest ER background [70]. For this reason the events can be tagged in the science condition runs. The ^{214}Po isotope has a half-life of $T_{1/2} \simeq 164.3 \mu\text{s}$ [134] and thus a range of $\simeq 50 \mu\text{m}$ in LXe [104]. Hence the decay is almost prompt and at approximately the same position after the β decay of its mother nucleus ^{214}Bi .

As first step, the monoenergetic α decays of the ^{214}Po are tagged. A XENONnT event is defined by peak(s) in a fixed time range around a selected peak identified by the “event builder” software. Due to the relatively short half-life of the ^{214}Po , its decay is always recorded within the same event as the preceding β decay of the ^{214}Bi . The information related to the first two S1 and four S2 signals (in area) is extracted. The largest S1 in the waveform is always associated with the high energetic α decay and it is denoted here as $S1_{\alpha}$. The second largest S1 in the waveform, occurring before the $S1_{\alpha}$ is named $S1_{\beta}$ and is related to the β decay. In order to tag the BiPo events, considering the $S1_{\alpha}$ and $S1_{\beta}$ properties, the following selection cuts are applied :

- $(1000 < S1_{\beta} < 35000) [\text{PE}]$: energy cut for the β decay. The lower limit is set to remove the less energetic events, which would result in a particularly challenging S1-based position reconstruction, mainly due to statistical fluctuations present in each channel.

- $S1_\alpha > 40000$ [PE] : the monochromatic α decay of ^{214}Po is energetic $E_\alpha \simeq 7.83$ MeV [134].
- $\text{times}_{S1_\alpha} - \text{times}_{S1_\beta} > 30 \mu\text{s}$: safe separation of the peaks and rejection of other background, pile-up interactions, and coincidences such as the ones from ^{220}Rn decay chain. If the goal of this analysis would be to estimate the BiPo activity concentration as done in [135], the value of the cut should be significantly decreased and other ways to improve the background reduction implemented. The signal efficiency, however, is not a fundamental aspect in the present analysis, since a sufficient statistics for the purpose are obtained in any case.
- $(S1_\alpha \text{ AFT}, S1_\alpha \text{ area})$ space : as can be seen in the left plot of figure 3.25 two different region are selected. The first one is identified considering the exponential band and limiting to events with $S1_\alpha \text{ AFT} < 0.43$, as for higher values a larger background contamination is found. The second one is obtained requiring $S1_\alpha \text{ area} > 40000$ and $S1_\alpha \text{ AFT} < 0.13$ up to the exponential band.

The result of the application of the S1-only selection cuts to tag ^{214}Po events can be seen in figure 3.25, where in the left plot the two sets of selected events (①, ②) are shown. The events outside the exponential band, ②, in the left plot of figure 3.25, are correctly tagged, in fact the right lifetime is also obtained by limiting only to them. The discrepancy in the behaviour in the $(S1_\alpha \text{ AFT}, S1_\alpha \text{ area})$ space can be attributed to the saturation of PMTs in the bottom array for α decays that happen close to it. This might result in a bias of $S1_\alpha \text{ AFT}$ towards larger values and a reduction in $S1_\alpha$ size. In the left plot of figure 3.25 on the left of the tagged ^{214}Po exponential band, another band, ③, mainly composed by alpha decays of ^{210}Po ($E_\alpha \simeq 5.41$ MeV), ^{222}Rn ($E_\alpha \simeq 5.59$ MeV), and ^{218}Po ($E_\alpha \simeq 6.11$ MeV) can be seen [133]. The contamination of the cathodic population from this second exponential band is mitigated by the first three S1-based selection cuts.

Figure 3.25: ^{214}Po population tagged with the S1-only cut selection. (Left) Visualization of the selected events in the $(S1_\alpha \text{ AFT}, S1_\alpha \text{ area})$ space. Two different populations can be distinguished: the one belonging to the exponential band, ①, and the cathodic one, ②, for more information see the text. (Right) Fit of the exponential decay for the ^{214}Po considering $\Delta T_{S1} = \text{times}_{S1_\alpha} - \text{times}_{S1_\beta}$. The obtained half-life $(164.8 \pm 4.7) \mu\text{s}$ is consistent with the measured value that can be found in the literature, $(164.3 \pm 0.2) \mu\text{s}$ [134].

Figure 3.26: S1 area distributions of the β decay of the ^{214}Bi and α decay of the ^{214}Po . The quantity is linked with the energy of the event through the [equation 2.21](#).

Although the α decay of ^{214}Po is more energetic than the β decay of the ^{214}Bi , this does not ensure that the size of the S2_α is larger than the one of the S2_β signal in the event. In fact, many liberated ionization electrons may recombine, due to the dense track of the α particle in the LXe, resulting in a quenched S2_α pattern. On the other hand, the size of the S2_β depends on the continuous energy spectrum of the β particle. For this reason, the correct matching of the S1-S2 pairs cannot be managed only with S2 signal size ordering. All the selected events contain up to a maximum of four S2 peaks, as the ^{214}Bi can decay to an excited state so that the α decay is followed by the emission of γ rays with different allowed energies. Among them, the most frequent are the ones at 609 keV (46.4 % probability), 1765 keV (15.4 %) and 1120 keV (15.1 %) [133]. The rejection of the S1 signals generated by the γ rays is reached thanks to the S1-based selection cuts. Those γ rays undergo multiple Compton scattering with attenuation lengths of $\mathcal{O}(\text{cm})$ in LXe [136], generating additional S2_γ signals in the waveform, which may be big enough to exceed in area the one from β decay, with a typical time distance of $\mathcal{O}(10\mu\text{s})$ from the S2_β .

Considering the time difference between the two S1 signals ΔT_{S1} as a variable for the matching, all the possible S2 signals pair combinations (six combinations) are considered. A time difference ΔT_{S2} can be derived from each of them. Afterwards, only the S2 pairs are accepted that satisfy the condition: $|\Delta T_{\text{S2}} - \Delta T_{\text{S1}}| < 2\mu\text{s}$. In case more matches are found, the combination with the larger S2 area is preferred. In order to increase the purity in the considered BiPo population, only the events with a difference less than 1 cm between the two z positions reconstructed with the standard method based on drift (see [section 3.2.2](#)) are considered.

In addition to being another independent validation, the application of the model to reconstruct the position of both the BiPo events allows to probe the resolution for energies lower than those considered in [figure 3.21](#). Since the two events should ideally be reconstructed in the same position, the resolution of the difference is equal to the one of the less energetic:

$$\Delta x_1 = x_{i,\text{Bi}} - x_{i,\text{Po}} \longrightarrow \sigma_{\Delta x_1} = \sqrt{\sigma_{x_{i,\text{Bi}}}^2 + \sigma_{x_{i,\text{Po}}}^2} \simeq \sigma_{x_{i,\text{Bi}}}, \quad (3.8)$$

where $\vec{x} = (x_0 = x, x_1 = y, x_2 = z)$.

Figure 3.27: Distribution of the difference between the reconstructed x (left) and z (right) position of the β decay of ^{214}Bi and α decay of ^{214}Po with the model trained on simulation (blue) and the one trained on data (orange).

In figure 3.26 the distributions of the S1 area for both the α decays of ^{214}Po and the β decays of the ^{214}Bi are shown. Due to the S1 area values of the latter, bearing in mind the results presented in figure 3.21, the resolution of the data-driven model is expected to get worse.

In fact, as can be seen in figure 3.27, there is no longer a substantial difference between the simulation and data trained model. The fact that this behaviour is due to the β decay of ^{214}Bi is confirmed by the Δz distributions in figure 3.28. On the one hand, the z position resolution of the α decays of the ^{214}Po , $\sigma_z = 1.31$ [cm], is compatible with the results presented in section 3.5.1, where here there is no more a cut based on the application of the simulation-driven model. Moreover, as already suggested by figure 3.21, there is no a significant bias in the z position reconstruction of the β decay of the ^{214}Bi , even if the S1 area values of those events are significantly lower than the ones present in the training set. On the other hand, up to S1 area $\simeq 10^4$ [PE] the 3D resolution, $r_{68\%}$, of the current data-driven model does not drastically get worse and it is preferable to the simulation-driven model. For lower values, the different composition of the two training sets in terms of signal amplitude starts to be crucial. It must not

Figure 3.28: (Left) 3D resolution for the difference between the reconstructed position of the β decay of ^{214}Bi and α decays of the ^{214}Po with the data trained (see section 3.5) and simulation trained model (see section 3.4.4). (Right) Distribution of the difference between the standard method based on drift (see section 3.2.2) and the reconstructed z position with the data trained model for the α decays of the ^{214}Po (orange) and β decay of ^{214}Bi (blue).

be forgotten, however, that one of the main reasons to prefer the data-driven model is not its better resolution, but the mitigation of the bias in the reconstruction of the z position for different depths. The current applications of the model, described in the [section 3.8](#), mainly concern energetic events. This is the reason why the training set of the data-driven model is currently composed as shown in [figure 3.21](#). One of the next steps will be a careful composition of the training set in order to enhance the performances over a broader range of S1 area values.

Summary and Outlook

This section summarises the thesis with an overview of its findings and indications of possible improvements and future developments of the work. The novel method introduced, based only on the prompt scintillation signal (S1), can play an important role in reconstructing the interaction position of events without a reliable charge signal (S2). Potential applications include the improvement of the event quality selection and the localization of possible charge insensitive regions inside the detector, which would impact the definition of the fiducial volume used in the XENONnT analysis.

3.7 Summary

Three-dimensional position reconstruction from the S1 signal is challenging mainly due to the relatively low amount of collected light and the spread of the patterns due to optical propagation, which strongly depends on the depth of the interaction inside the time projection chamber (TPC).

The event position (x,y,z) is predicted using a deep learning model, taking as an input only the S1 signal detected by each photomultiplier tube (PMT) from both the top and bottom array. In order to exploit convolutional neural networks with the hexagonal PMT arrangement, the axial transformation is used. A random search hyperparameter optimization is exploited to find a performing predictor. It is necessary to achieve a trade-off between reconstruction performances and execution time per event, limited by the needs of the analysis flow of the XENONnT experiment. Proof of principle studies are performed, training and testing the model on simulated patterns.

The selected simulation-driven model is applied, next, to α decays present in ^{220}Rn calibration data, revealing, in particular through the results for the z position, a mismatch between the simulated patterns and the real data. To improve the accuracy of the predictions and move forward the matching campaign between simulation and data, training sets with different liquid xenon absorption lengths are tried and a new optical map is tested, obtaining significant improvements.

To overcome the current discrepancy between simulation and data, a data-driven model is presented using the reconstruction obtained with standard methods after the corrections for the supervised training. This is done as an algorithm based on the S1 signal cannot approach the resolution of methods based on S2 signal and drift time measurement. A noteworthy improvement in the prediction accuracy and, most importantly, a mitigation of the biases in the reconstruction of the z position, are achieved with respect to the simulation-driven predictor.

The data-driven model is trained and tested on energetic α decays from ^{220}Rn calibration data, in a S1 area range between $(20 - 140) \cdot 10^3$ photoelectrons [PE]. The 3D resolution reached values down to $r_{68\%} \simeq 2$ cm for the most energetic events. Taking together all the α decays from ^{220}Rn calibration data as a test set, the resolutions obtained correspond to: $\sigma_x = 2.26$ [cm], $\sigma_y = 2.36$ [cm], and $\sigma_z = 1.98$ [cm]. The performances for events with an S1 area poorly represented in the training set is shown to undergo a resolution degradation without introducing any biased behavior. The robustness of the model against systematic effects, such as fluctuations due to PMT's gain instabilities and missing PMTs, is verified and studied. In conclusion, the final selected data and simulation-driven models are applied to the coincident events of the β decay of the ^{214}Bi nucleus and the α decay of ^{214}Po to estimate their resolution in a data-driven way. Those results allow a comparison of the performances of the two models for S1 area values much lower than the minimum present in the training set of the data-driven model, pointing that, currently, the latter is preferable in terms of precision up to a S1 area $\simeq 10^4$ [PE].

3.8 Outlook

Current models are an important proof of principle demonstrating the viability of S1-only position reconstruction with deep learning in the XENONnT experiment. The following steps can be performed to improve the performance. First of all, the current campaign to match the simulation and data will increase the accuracy of simulation-driven model's predictions on real events. Regarding the data-driven model, likewise, there are many possibilities of progress. Among those, the most important ones are the outward bias in the reconstruction of the events' radius in the center of the TPC and the bias still slightly present in predicting the z position for different depths. Good improvements have been achieved during the thesis project in those directions and they are subjects for further investigation.

The forthcoming availability of new computing resources from the Midway3 [125] computing cluster will allow increasing the complexity of the model on equal runtime per event. The impact of that possibility on the generalization capabilities of the predictor and on the mitigation of the previously mentioned biases will be subject to a more in-depth analysis. Events with lower energies can be added to the training set to exploit the potential of the data-driven model fully.

Preliminary field simulation studies indicate that the usage of the field shaping rings can result in charge insensitive regions at the percent level of the total active volume [106]. An ongoing analysis tries to find this effect in the data using the method introduced in this work. The followed strategy is to map the distribution of the events with an inconsistency between the reconstructed position from the S2 signal and drift time with the one from the S1 signal. The quantification of an S2 insensitive mass and the determination of its position would be a fundamental factor for the analysis of the physics reach of the experiment, impacting the fiducial volume definition.

The identification of a discrepancy in the reconstruction of the position between methods based on the S1 and S2 signals indicates potential of this algorithm for the definition of a data quality cuts to identify accidental coincidences for the forthcoming XENONnT analysis. As the position reconstruction from the prompt scintillation signal is a new possibility, the full range of potential applications is yet to be identified in its entirety.

APPENDIX A

Performances Slicing the Detector

Some additional plots are shown in this appendix to better check the data-driven model performances in different areas of the detector, trying to decouple the variation for different radii with that for different depths.

A.1 Performance (X,Y,R) vs R^2 for Small Z Regions

The detector is segmented into four horizontal slices. The shown plots seem reasonably follow the behaviour of the ones presented and commented in [section 3.5.2](#), integrated over the z position. The most important variations can be observed in the reconstruction of the radius and they will be subject of further investigation.

Figure A.1: Reconstruction of the x position as a function of the squared “true” radius (S_2 based reconstructed) in different z slices.

A.1. Performance (X,Y,R) vs R^2 for Small Z Regions

Figure A.2: Reconstruction of the radius as a function of the squared “true” radius (S2 based reconstructed) in different z slices.

Figure A.3: Reconstruction of the z position as a function of the squared “true” radius (S2 based reconstructed) in different z slices.

A.2 Performance (X,Y,R) vs Z for Small R Regions

The detector is segmented into four concentric slices. As in the previous subsection, the most important variations can be observed in the reconstruction of the radius.

Figure A.4: Reconstruction of the x position as a function of the “true” z position (drift based reconstruction) in different R slices.

A.2. Performance (X,Y,R) vs Z for Small R Regions

Figure A.5: Reconstruction of the radius as a function of the “true” z position (drift based reconstructed) in different R slices.

Figure A.6: Reconstruction of the z position as a function of the “true” z position (drift based reconstructed) in different R slices.

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Only loving, only knowing matter.
Not the fact of having loved, or
having known.

Pier Paolo Pasolini

Non nobis.

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